

PLEDGE

Politics of Grievance and Democratic Governance

**Research Report: PLEDGE
Conceptual Framework, v1**

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Executive Summary

The PLEDGE Conceptual Framework offers a theoretical foundation for understanding the emotional dynamics of grievance politics. It explores how emotions—triggered by perceived social or political injustices—shape political engagement, influencing both pro- and anti-democratic behaviours.

At the core of the PLEDGE Conceptual Framework are two key emotional mechanisms:

- **EMRes (Emotional Mechanism of Resentment):** Linked to resentment, envy, and hostility, often fueling polarisation or reactionary politics.
- **EMSoS (Emotional Mechanism of Solidarity-Oriented Sharing):** Encourages prosocial emotions like empathy and collective care, supporting solidarity and inclusive action.

Developed as a **common language model**, the PLEDGE Conceptual Framework is a living document, intended to bridge disciplines and offer consistent use of concepts across the PLEDGE research teams and beyond. It connects emotional processes with social, cultural, and political contexts, offering tools to analyze how grievances emerge, evolve, and translate into political action.

The framework defines key concepts—such as **grievance politics** and its **emotional economy**—and outlines the emotional, psychological, and societal dynamics behind them. It also aligns closely with the **PLEDGE Codebook**, ensuring that theoretical insights directly inform empirical research.

Together, the framework and codebook form the backbone of PLEDGE’s research strategy, enabling a deeper understanding of how emotions drive democratic engagement and disaffection.

1. Introduction

1.1. About PLEDGE

PLEDGE is a Horizon Europe-funded project focusing on the emotional dynamics of political grievances and their implications for democratic politics. The PLEDGE project engages researchers, policymakers, and citizens in a collective effort to better understand citizens' emotions and develop practices and tools that promote emotionally responsive democratic governance and political communication and foster pro-democratic forms of civic engagement.

1.2. Why a PLEDGE Conceptual Framework

The PLEDGE Conceptual Framework sets the foundation for theorizing and analyzing grievance politics across all PLEDGE studies and beyond. It defines a shared set of core concepts and emotional mechanisms, enabling consistent application across different disciplines and methodological approaches.

This framework critically synthesizes key debates and definitions drawn from political science, political psychology, sociology, psychology, political communication, international relations, philosophy and related disciplines. It brings together diverse perspectives on how grievances emerge, how they are emotionally experienced, and how they shape political behaviour and democratic engagement.

The framework is designed to evolve through empirical testing and refinement, ensuring it remains adaptable to real-world complexities. It is closely aligned with the **PLEDGE Codebook**, which translates conceptual insights into operational indicators. Developed in parallel, the framework and codebook ensure that theory and empirical design and analysis are tightly integrated—supporting systematic, cross-contextual analysis of the emotional dimensions of grievance politics.

Who Is the Conceptual Framework For?

The PLEDGE Conceptual Framework is primarily intended for researchers, data analysts, policymakers interested in the understanding of grievance politics and its emotional dynamics

Data analysts use the framework to interpret the meaning behind coded data—whether from interviews, surveys, focus groups, or media analysis—applying conceptual clarity to both qualitative and quantitative findings.

Policymakers and practitioners are secondary users. While academic in origin, the framework offers practical value for designing emotionally responsive governance strategies and public communication that reflect citizens’ lived experiences.

External collaborators—including NGOs, advocacy groups, and civic organizations—can also benefit. The framework helps them better understand the emotional contours of grievance politics and supports more inclusive, empathetic approaches to democratic engagement.

1.4. How was the PLEDGE Conceptual Framework created: Notes on Methodology

The PLEDGE Conceptual Framework draws on the original PLEDGE proposal, insights from the literature review, and continuous exchanges at consortium meetings, workshops and conferences. While not all background references appear in the final version, selected citations from the broader conceptualization work have been retained to offer context and enrich the report’s analytical depth.

2. Conceptual Framework

2.1 Introduction

The PLEDGE Common Language Conceptual Framework aims to provide an empirically testable model of the psychological, socio-cultural, and political dynamics underlying anti- and pro-democratic grievance politics. At the heart of the PLEDGE Conceptual Framework is a distinction between *grievances* and ***grievance politics***—the latter referring to a mode of political engagement centered on the expression and mobilization of grievances. The framework also introduces two key emotional mechanisms: **EMRes** (Emotional Mechanism of Resentment) and **EMSoS** (Emotional Mechanism of Solidarity-Oriented Sharing). These mechanisms serve as the conceptual foundation for understanding how emotions shape political preferences, attachments, and behaviours.

This research report integrates perspectives from social sciences (political science, political psychology, sociology, psychology, philosophy, international relations, and communication studies). It was designed to provide a shared foundation for all stages of the PLEDGE project, ensuring consistency across data collection, analysis, and interpretation.

The report outlines core concepts, definitions, and indicators, and it is developed alongside the **PLEDGE Codebook**.

2.2 PLEDGE Conceptual Framework: Emotional Mechanisms at the Heart of Grievance Politics

The PLEDGE Conceptual Framework seeks to understand how grievances emerge, how emotions shape political behaviour, and how these dynamics interact with democratic processes.

Grievances and Their Roots

The framework builds on theories that explain how grievances are formed, including:

- ✓ **Urban-rural divide:** Resource inequality and neglect fuel resentment, especially in marginalized rural areas.
- ✓ **Cultural backlash:** Tensions between progressive and traditional values drive intergenerational and ideological divides.
- ✓ **Socio-economic pressures:** Economic hardship and inequality often underpin political discontent, especially when combined with demographic change or perceived cultural threat.

The Emotional Undercurrent that Sustains Grievances

While much existing research sees emotions as *results* of grievances, PLEDGE shifts the focus to how emotions themselves actively shape political preferences and behaviours. Political psychology shows that emotions like fear and anger influence decision-making—but PLEDGE broadens this to include a fuller emotional range, such as envy, shame, humiliation, inefficacious anger, empathy, gratitude, pride, and resentment.

This expanded emotional perspective is dynamic, emphasizing how emotions interact with identities, values, and political contexts in feedback loops that shape how individuals engage with politics.

Emotionality and Grievance Politics in Policy and Governance

Policy studies have begun to recognize the role of emotion in governance but often treat it as secondary to rational processes. PLEDGE challenges this view, arguing for emotionally responsive policymaking. It emphasizes that emotional expressions—like disaffection, hope, or frustration—are meaningful signals of citizen needs, not irrational noise.

Democratic Innovations and Emotion

Emotional dynamics play a key role in democratic innovations such as participatory and deliberative processes. These settings often evoke strong emotions that can polarize as well as build solidarity. PLEDGE explores how emotional design in democratic practices can help channel grievances constructively, supporting more inclusive and empathetic engagement.

The PLEDGE Core Framework

At the centre of the PLEDGE framework (Figure 1) are two emotional mechanisms:

- ✓ **EMRes (Ressentiment):** A mechanism driven by emotions like envy, humiliation, or hate, often leading to anti-democratic reactions.
- ✓ **EMSoS (Solidarity-Oriented Sharing):** A mechanism that transforms negative emotions into collective bonds, enabling inclusive and pro-democratic action.

These mechanisms help explain how grievances become emotionally charged and politically expressed—either in divisive or constructive ways.

Understanding Grievance Politics Holistically

PLEDGE treats grievance politics as individual *and* collective, shaped by psychological, socio-cultural, and political forces. It incorporates factors like ideologies, historical narratives, leadership styles, media influence, and emotional norms, recognizing how these shape the trajectory of grievances toward different democratic outcomes.

Building Democratic Sensibility in the Context of Grievance Politics

The PLEDGE framework embraces a co-creative and stakeholder-driven approach. Grounded in democratic design principles, it aims to promote emotionally sensitive governance that channels grievances into productive democratic engagement—disrupting cycles of toxicity and fostering healthier discourse.

Figure 1 – The PLEDGE Conceptual Framework of the Emotional Economy of Anti- /Pro-democratic Grievance Politics

In the sections that follow, we define the core PLEDGE concepts illustrated in Figure 1. Each concept is supported by relevant references and flagged for potential further development as standalone entries. We also outline how these concepts are **operationalized** in PLEDGE - across methods such as longitudinal surveys, experiments, focus groups, interviews, and media content analysis.

2.3 Thematic Organization

The PLEDGE Conceptual Framework is organized into thematic sections that reflect the key dimensions of emotional dynamics in grievance politics. This structure mirrors the PLEDGE Codebook.

Grievances and Grievance Politics: Defines core concepts of dissatisfaction and perceived injustice, showing how grievances evolve into collective political expressions within broader social, economic, and political contexts.

Emotional Mechanisms (EMRes & EMSoS):

- ✓ *EMRes* captures the internalization and transformation of negative emotions (e.g., envy, shame) into resentment and identity shifts.

- ✓ *EMSoS* highlights how similar emotions can be shared and transformed into solidarity and inclusive collective identities. These mechanisms help explain divergent emotional and political pathways triggered by grievances.

Input and Output Emotions: Distinguishes between initial emotional triggers (input: shame, envy, anger) and resulting emotional states (output: pride, resentment, hope). This helps track emotional trajectories in political contexts.

Psychological Triggers: Identifies internal drivers of emotional responses—such as emotional needs, trust, and cynicism—that explain why certain grievances resonate more deeply within individuals or groups.

Psychological Orientations, Values, and Identities: Covers orientations (e.g., authoritarianism), values (e.g., security), and identities (e.g., partisan, ideological) that shape emotional interpretation and political alignment.

Socio-Cultural Triggers: Defines cultural dynamics like nostalgia, emotional norms, and governance practices that shape emotional responses to political events and messages.

Political Triggers: Focuses on how leadership, media, and policymaking serve as catalysts for emotional engagement and grievance mobilization.

Political Preferences and Behaviours: Categorizes forms of political participation, dissent (e.g., radicalization), and disengagement (e.g., apathy), revealing how emotions influence democratic involvement and extremism.

Democratic Innovations and New Approaches to Democratic Society: Explores emotionally responsive democratic practices and innovations, including emotion-sensitive design, to strengthen inclusive and empathetic governance.

3. Concepts

3.1 Grievances, Grievance Politics, Emotional Economy of Grievance Politics

3.1.1 Grievances

Definition

A grievance is a real or perceived wrong or injustice that an individual or group believes has been inflicted upon them. It often refers to a feeling of resentment or dissatisfaction regarding unfair treatment, mistreatment, or violation of rights (Capelos et al. 2022; Dictionary.com). Grievances can arise in personal, social and political contexts.

How Grievance(s) contribute to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

PLEDGE seeks to explore how grievances lead to pro- and anti-social outcomes while simultaneously transforming the values, identities, and emotions of the individuals or groups involved. To illuminate this complex dynamic, PLEDGE focuses on the study of emotional transformation processes, referred to as emotional mechanisms (EMs) (Elster 1999; Salice & Salmela 2022). By mapping these emotional pathways, PLEDGE seeks to examine the nuanced ways emotions orient political engagement and action.

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3.1.2 Grievance Politics

Definition

Grievance politics refers to a contemporary mode of political engagement driven primarily by perceived injustices and emotional grievances, rather than traditional factors like ideological commitments, partisan loyalty, economic self-interest, or evaluations of salient policy issues. It emphasizes personal and collective feelings of resentment (qua moral anger) or victimization, shaping political behavior through resentment-driven grievances rather than

through established political identities or rational calculations (Capelos et al., 2023; Capelos et al., 2024).

How grievance politics contribute to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

PLEDGE studies the emotional dynamics of grievance politics, with the aim to develop practices and tools that can promote emotionally responsive democratic governance and political communication and foster pro-democratic forms of civic engagement.

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3.1.3 Neighbouring concepts: Anti-preferences, Angry Politics, Backlash Politics

Anti-preferences

Anti-preferences refer to political attitudes and behaviors that are shaped more by what individuals or groups oppose rather than what they support (Capelos & Katsanidou, 2018). In anti-preference politics, people are motivated less by ideological commitments or specific policy goals and more by a strong desire to reject or undermine particular leaders, parties, or policies. This is closely linked to grievance politics, as individuals may express their political identity through opposition to perceived injustices or threats, leading them to vote or act in ways that prioritize negating an undesirable outcome rather than advancing a positive agenda (negative partisanship). Anti-preferences reflect a "politics of negation," where opposition is the central driver of engagement, and are therefore attitudinally distinct from any propositions, which are guided by an aspiration to achieve or endorse specific goals or ideals. As such, anti-preferences are a neighboring concept to Reactionism (see entry), where opposition itself becomes the main purpose of political participation.

Angry politics

Angry politics revolves around the mobilization of anger as a dominant force in shaping political behavior. Anger is often triggered by perceived injustice, betrayal, or unfulfilled promises, and it can fuel political movements, protests, and voting patterns. Like grievance politics, angry politics is deeply personal and emotional. While the emotional intensity of anger can energize political participation and polarize public discourse, the emotional undercurrent of grievance politics is resentment, which harbors reactionary responses which are primarily passive.

Backlash politics

Backlash politics refers to movements that arise in response to perceived social, cultural, or political changes that are seen as threatening by certain groups. These movements often emerge from grievances related to a loss of status, privilege, or cultural identity, and they seek to reverse or resist progressive reforms. The emotional dynamics here are about fear, anger, and nostalgia for a perceived loss of power, status, or cultural dominance. Backlash politics and grievance politics share their strong dissatisfaction with the current state of affairs. However, backlash politics aims to preserve or restore traditional norms and power structures, while grievance politics could be forward or backward looking. Moreover, grievance politics is a way of engaging with politics focusing primarily on perceived injustices and its emotional responses of resentment and inefficacious anger are expressed through an unapologetic sense of morally righteous victimhood.

3.1.4 Emotional Economy of Grievance Politics

Definition

The emotional economy of grievance politics refers to the complex interplay of emotions, social dynamics, and political contexts that shape and influence individuals' grievances within democratic societies. This concept recognizes that emotions are not merely individual experiences; they are also socially constructed and commodified, impacting collective behaviour, political discourse, and policy-making processes. The emotional economy highlights how emotions can be mobilized, manipulated, and exchanged in political contexts, often serving as catalysts for action or sources of division.

How the Emotional Economy of Grievance Politics contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

The concept of the emotional economy of grievance politics is central to the PLEDGE conceptual framework, as it captures the intricate web of emotions, social forces, and political conditions that shape grievances in democratic contexts. By framing emotions as socially

constructed, circulated, monetized, and exchanged, PLEDGE moves beyond viewing emotions as isolated individual experiences, emphasizing instead how they influence and drive collective behavior, political discourse, and policymaking. The emotional economy illustrates how emotions can be strategically mobilized or manipulated, potentially fueling solidarity and democratic engagement or, conversely, deepening divisions and grievances. This perspective allows PLEDGE to analyze the ways emotions become embedded in political actions, providing a lens through which the dynamic role of emotions in grievance politics can be understood and addressed.

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3.2 Emotional Mechanisms of Grievance Politics

3.2.1 Emotional Mechanisms

Definition

An emotional mechanism is an emotional transformation process in which input emotions (initial emotional states) transform into output emotions (resulting emotional states) that influence cognitive, motivational, moral, and behavioural responses to social and political stimuli. According to Salice and Salmela (2022), “emotional mechanisms explain transformations of discrete emotions into other specific emotions by showing the process that leads to transformations of this kind, their constituent elements, and their mutual relationship” (p. 50).

How Emotional Mechanisms contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

PLEDGE recognises the importance of examining emotional mechanisms to understand the complexities of political behavior and social relations, illuminating how emotions and

sentiments can either unite or divide individuals and groups within political contexts. A deeper understanding of the EMRes and EMSoS mechanisms is central to PLEDGE's objectives. By examining the complex interplay of emotions, values, identities, beliefs, and political behaviours that take place with these emotional mechanisms, and which translate to support for or active involvement in anti-democratic or pro-democratic politics, PLEDGE aims to advance empirically grounded theories. This knowledge is essential not only for understanding why individuals may support anti-democratic movements but also for developing strategies to transform these anti-democratic grievances into pro-democratic civic engagement. It is through such insights that PLEDGE seeks to illuminate pathways that encourage constructive participation and foster democratic resilience.

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3.2.2 Emotional Mechanism of Ressentiment (EMRes)

Definition

EM Ressentiment (EMRes), is an emotional mechanism through which feelings of frustration and threats to self-worth, stemming from the impression of repeated failures and insufficiency and manifested as envy, shame, humiliation, and impotent anger, transform into resentment, indignation, contempt, and hatred directed toward outgroups. The individual's self-identity—whether personal or social—shifts from one of perceived inferiority to a newly forged identity of nobility and superiority. Simultaneously, the value of what was once desired but unattainable transforms into something undesirable and worthless, akin to the fox in Aesop's fable of "sour grapes," who dismisses the grapes that it cannot reach (Aeschbach, 2017; Demertzis, 2020). While EMRes begins with feelings of inefficacy, it retains this sense of inadequacy, characterized by a fragile attachment to in-group members, leading to insecurity (Salmela & Capelos, 2021).

Neighbouring concepts

While concepts such as envy, shame, humiliation, anger, resentment, indignation, contempt, hatred, and victimhood may be closely related to resentment, they should not be viewed as synonymous with it. Recognizing their nuances helps to clarify the unique role of resentment in the landscape of emotional experiences related to political and social grievances. Please

see entries for envy, shame, humiliation, anger, resentment, indignation, contempt, hatred, victimhood.

How EM Resentment contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

In PLEDGE, resentment is conceptualized as the key emotional mechanism driving anti-democratic grievances. This process involves a shift in self-identity: individuals move from feelings of inferiority to a perception of superiority and moral righteousness. Additionally, the value of previously desired but unattainable goals is redefined as undesirable and worthless. When studied statically, resentment is seen as a complex emotional outcome within grievance politics.

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3.2.3 Resentment as a Complex Emotional Experience

Definition

Ressentiment is a latent construct which contains self-targeting emotions such as envy, shame, humiliation, and helpless/hopeless (inefficacious) anger, other-targeting emotions such as resentment, indignation, contempt, and hatred, a sense of moral righteous victimhood, as well as the dynamic process of transvaluation as the transformation of the

values of the coveted and unattainable object and one's sense of self (Salmela & Capelos, 2021; Demertzis, 2020).

3.2.4 Emotional Mechanism of Solidarity-Oriented Sharing (EMSoS)

Definition

EMSoS is conceptualized as the emotional mechanism that transforms self-targeting negative emotions such as envy, shame, humiliation, and inefficacious anger that threaten the self-worth and social recognitions of individuals, into other-directed negative emotions such as resentment and indignation, but also pride, joy, and hope. The emotional transformation operates through reappraisals in which the driver emotions are shared with peer others, which results in the reinforcement of existing values and identity of the subjects (Salmela & von Scheve, 2018; Salmela & Szanto, forthcoming).

How EM Solidarity-Oriented Sharing contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

In PLEDGE, Solidarity Oriented Sharing is the EM that supports prodemocratic ways of processing grievances/grievance politics. EMSoS transforms envy, shame, humiliation and inefficacious anger into collective democratic resentment, indignation, hope, and pride. The self-identity (personal & social) of the individual as inferior transforms into emancipated and optimistic. The value of what was desired and unattainable transforms into a collective goal to pursue with peers. In this way, EMSoS starts with inefficacy and transforms it into efficacy, through secure and solidary bonds with in-group others. PLEDGE expects EMSoS to operate when there is emotional reflexivity, and conducive feeling rules for social sharing.

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3.2.5 Solidarity as a Complex Emotional Experience

Definition

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Solidarity is complex emotional experience of social cohesion that binds individuals together within a society or social group, it is the “bond of unity between individuals, united around a shared purpose, feeling of sympathy, or sense of mutual responsibility” (Durkheim, 1984 [1893]).

How Solidarity contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Solidarity is the ideal manifested in reciprocal sharing of grievances with peer others and forming strong bonds of unity with them. Groups with political solidarity are capable of coming together based on common interests in opposition to injustice or oppression, seeking to find peaceful and constructive ways of resisting and overcoming them. PLEDGE expects to find solidarity in social and political movements manifesting EMSoS.

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3.3 Emotionality

PLEDGE’s starting point is that while democratic policymakers may be tempted to view intense emotions as irrational or as obstacles to sound decision-making, dismissing them as inherently harmful to democratic processes is a limited perspective. Emotions are, in fact, deeply embedded in politics and policymaking, and addressing today’s complex challenges requires an in-depth understanding of the emotional dynamics that drive public engagement, shape political behavior, and influence policy outcomes.

PLEDGE approaches intense emotionality as a flashpoint which highlights underlying social, political, and economic crises, and reveals uncomfortable truths about inequities in resource distribution, growing wealth disparity, and local marginalization—experienced as a loss of dignity or humiliation (Salmela & Capelos, 2021; Demertzis, 2020). Recognizing the complex emotionality of grievance politics, PLEDGE goes beyond extant research approaches which identify anger as the main emotional driver and the main expression of grievances. These approaches, although parsimonious, run into difficulty when trying to explain diverse anti-/pro-democratic preferences and actions resulting from grievance. PLEDGE examines

emotional mechanisms which connect input and output emotions to explain when and how grievances lead to anti-/pro-democratic preferences and actions.

PLEDGE focuses on individual as well as collective emotions by understanding emotionality as socially and culturally constructed.

3.3.1 Individual Emotions

Definition

Emotions are spontaneous responses to perceived or anticipated negative or positive changes in the state of our matters of concern. They are affective states with brief onset, short duration, relatively high intensity, as well as specific targets and action tendencies, and they come in discrete types such as anger, fear, disgust, sadness, and joy (e.g. Ekman & Davidson, 1994). A componential view about emotions that is widely accepted in contemporary philosophy, psychology, and sociology sees emotions involving several synchronous components such as appraisals, autonomous nervous system changes, motor activation, and subjective experience (see e.g., Scherer, 2009).

In philosophy, emotions are conceived as felt evaluations with a target, a formal object and a focus (Goldie, 2000; Helm, 2010). The target is the particular object of emotion, such as an aggressively barking dog in fear. The formal object is the evaluative category of being dangerous in terms of which the factual properties the dog are evaluated as fearful. Typically, each emotion type correlates with (or is sensitive to) a specific formal object: fear to danger, pride to achievements, indignation to moral injustice, and so on (Kenny, 1963). Finally, fear of the dog is made intelligible by concern for your wellbeing, which is the focus of this emotional episode. Concerns that ground emotions can also focus on other people and issues besides the self.

Neighbouring concepts

affects, feelings, sentiments, moods, emotional traits

How individual emotions contribute to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

PLEDGE studies dynamic relations between values, identities, emotions, and political orientations. It identifies emotions as drivers of mechanisms that explain transformations of discrete emotions into other specific emotions, while inducing changes in values and emotions in transformations of this kind. PLEDGE hypothesizes that the main difference between EMRes and EMSoS resides in the processing of self-directed negative emotions of

shame, envy, humiliation, and inefficacious anger; whether they are repressed or socially shared with others. If these emotions are repressed, they may not be reported in the scale that studies experiences of discrete emotions. However, they may be felt but not socially shared with others, so it is important to look at outcome emotions of EMs as well. Here we expect to see differences between EMRes and EMSoS besides resentment and indignation that associate with both EMs, albeit with somewhat dissimilar properties (see Resentment, Indignation). With EMRes, we also expect to also find contempt, disgust, hatred, nostalgia, and hubristic pride, whereas we expect EMSoS to associate with hope, optimism, enthusiasm, joy, and pride.

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3.3.2 Collective Emotions

Definition

“Synchronous convergence in affective responding across individuals towards a specific event or object” (von Scheve & Ismer 2013, p. 411).

“Persons X and Y share an emotion, or equivalently have a collective emotion if, (a) X and Y experience an emotion of the same type with similar: (i) evaluative content and (ii) affective experience; and (b) X and Y are mutually aware that (a).” (Salmela & Nagatsu, 2016, p. 36).

Neighbouring concepts

emotional climates, feeling rules

How collective emotions contribute to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Collective emotions are important in validating and reinforcing the outcome emotions of EMsRes and EMSoS as well as the identities and values to which these emotions relate. PLEDGE hypothesizes that partially different collective emotions are felt and expressed by participants and supporters of anti- and pro-democratic political movements. We expect to find more other-directed negative collective emotions such as anger, resentment, indignation, disgust, contempt, and hatred among supporters of political movements whose emotional dynamics is mediated by EMRes. Instead, we expect to find both self-directed and other-directed collective emotions such as envy, shame, humiliation, and frustration, in addition to anger, resentment, and indignation, among supporters of political movements whose emotional dynamics is mediated by EMSoS. We also expect to find more positive collective emotions, such as joy, happiness, pride, hope, and enthusiasm in the latter group, while we hypothesize nostalgia and hubristic pride to be more prevalent in the former group.

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3.4 Input Emotions of EMs

3.4.1 Envy

Definition

Envy is pain at the good fortune of others (Aristotle, *Rhetoric*, Bk II, Chapter 10).

Envy is a propensity to view the well-being of others with distress, even though it does not detract from one's own. [It is] a reluctance to see our own well-being overshadowed by another's because the standard we use to see how well off we are is not the intrinsic worth of our own well-being but how it compares with that of others. [Envy] aims, at least in terms

of one's wishes, at destroying others' good fortune (Kant, *The Metaphysics of Morals* 6, p. 459).

Envy is an aversive reaction to a perceived inferiority to a similar other, with regard to a good that is relevant to the sense of identity of the envier (Protasi, 2016, p.2).

Envy occurs when a person lacks another's superior quality, achievement, or possession and either desires it or wishes that the other lacked it (Parrott & Smith, 1993, p. 906).

How envy contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Envy has a key role in EMRes. The frustrations and threat to self-worth are experienced after repeated failures as envy (PLEDGE, Section 1.2.1.1). PLEDGE theorizes envy as one of the input emotions of resentment, and therefore as a key constituent of the emotionality of grievance politics. PLEDGE notes that grievance politics is fed by social disparities and sense of injustice. The distinction between benign and malicious envy can allow us to explore pro-democratic and anti-democratic expressions of grievance politics.

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3.4.2 Shame

Definition

Painful, negative, global and self-conscious emotional state elicited by one's violation of some moral standards, rules and Goals (SRGs), so that one feels exposed to the eye of another person sensing oneself as worthless and powerless (Lewis, 2000).

How shame contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Shame has been studied by several consortium members (PLEDGE, Sections 1.1.1, 1.2.4) and it is negatively related to pride and positively with humiliation (PLEDGE, Section 1.2.1). PLEDGE sees shame not just as something deeply personal but socially generated by social, economic and political conditions. Socio-economic relegation, caused by neo-liberal policies that puts the blame for failures and misfortunes on individuals, whatever circumstances, generates humiliation alongside an urgent need for social recognition and alleviation of shame articulated through privately and publicly expressed grievances. Shame is also considered to be a discursive weapon in political antagonism by diminishing the value of one's opponents. In this sense, shame and shaming, as well as the politicians' promise to relieve shame, are integral to grievance politics and therefore the investigation of this emotion plays a crucial role to the PLEDGE project. Shame is one of the key emotions conceptually relevant in transformations of EMs from EMRes to EMSoS. Shame is integral to EMRes.

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3.4.3 Humiliation

Definition

To feel one unjustly deprived of something considered rightfully a part of one's identity (Muenster, 2024, p. 181).

“People feel humiliated when they are forced or kept away from a position they perceive as being ‘rightfully theirs’ within a group, network or hierarchy to which they feel they ‘rightfully belong’” (Smith, 2006, p. 30).

Neighbouring concepts

Shame, embarrassment, guilt, affliction, distrust, revenge.

How humiliation contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

The concept of humiliation is linked in PLEDGE to the dynamics of grievance politics, in relation to anti- and pro-democratic ways of processing grievances. Humiliation is identified as one of the negative emotions, alongside envy, shame, and inefficacious anger, that is transformed in EMRes into resentment, indignation, contempt, and hatred, directed towards outgroups. In EMSos, envy, shame, humiliation and inefficacious anger are transformed through social sharing into collective democratic resentment (Engels 2015) towards those blamed for what is at stake and also hope.

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3.4.4 Anger (inefficacious in resentment)

Definition

Anger is a discrete emotion with a defined object, usually short-lived, and generates action tendencies. Anger arises as a response to the appraisal of an event which is not in the individual’s control, seen as an obstruction or infringement to reaching a goal or satisfying a need. It is bound to personal or social expectations, and results in physiological changes and mental readiness, which prepare an individual for action (Capelos, 2013; Ekman, 2004; Frijda, 2004; Lazarus, 1993; Roseman & Evdokas, 2004).

How (inefficacious) anger contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

PLEDGE primarily studies anger in the context of anti- and prodemocratic grievance politics. PLEDGE focuses on moral instances of anger (such as resentment and indignation) which can

be constructive or destructive responses to unjust circumstances. The management of non-moral anger and its influence on the processing of politically relevant information may also become relevant in the context of EM Ressentiment and EM Solidarity-Oriented Sharing. PLEDGE draws on recent studies which note that visible and loudly expressed anger and frustration by citizens can conceal anxiety, insecurity and uncertainty, and also painful emotions of humiliation, envy, shame (PLEDGE, Section 1.1.1). We theorize that anger has weak ties to uncertainty in comparison with fear (PLEDGE, Section 1.2.1). We also note that authoritarian populists adopt language which fosters anger (PLEDGE, Section 1.1.1). We also identify the role of anger in the emotional mechanism of solidarity-oriented sharing (EMSoS). Here inefficacious, righteous anger is triggered and transforms through social sharing into collective democratic resentment (PLEDGE, Section 1.2.1.1).

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3.4.5 Anxiety

Definition

Anxiety is a state of unease about a distal, potentially negative outcome that is uncertain or unpredictable (Labar, 2018, p. 751).

Anxiety is a future-oriented emotion characterized by marked negative affect, bodily symptoms of tension, and chronic apprehension, in contrast to fear which is an immediate alarm reaction to present danger characterized by strong escapist action tendencies (Barlow et al., 2003).

Neighbouring concepts

Fear, distress, worry

How anxiety contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Provided that grievance politics is fed by uncertainty related emotionality, anxiety is likely to help explore pro-democratic and anti-democratic versions of relevant attitudes and predispositions. The concept of anxiety is discussed in PLEDGE as part of the emotional response tied to grievance politics and contemporary sociopolitical crises. Anxiety is discussed in relation to other negative emotions, such as fear, insecurity, and uncertainty, that can be manipulated by political actors. Anxiety, together with fear and uncertainty, are defined as norm-following emotions that may have paradoxically positive effect on support for preventive measures through group-based control restoration mechanisms (a tendency to restore control by sticking to agentic and powerful groups).

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3.4.6 Fear

Definition

Fear is an unpleasant prospect-based emotion about the prospect of an undesirable event (Ortony et al., 1988, pp. 109-14).

Fear is the emotion of anticipated danger (Oatley & Jenkins, 1996, p. 260).

Neighbouring concepts

Anxiety

How fear contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

By and large, grievances are given rise to in virtue of extant or imminent social inequalities, perceived injustice, and threats of regarding the loss of status. Fear of social degradation is publicly articulated in the form of grievances against the elites, the establishment, or through goat scaping repertoires. According to the conceptual apparatus employed in PLEDGE, fear stands as an input emotion that supplies the EMs of Ressentiment and Solidarity-Oriented Sharing so that it can be transformed either into, let's say, hatred, despair, contempt, distrust, or shame; or it may turn into trust, hope, interest, or gratitude. Much of anti-political stances, backlash politics and anti-democratic grievance politics derive from fear and the "culture of fear" for that matter; PLEDGE attempts to explore the paths through which afflicted citizenry may vigilantly cultivate a sort of "liberalism of fear", namely to secure freedom from the fear of political cruelty toward solidaristic politics.

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3.4.7 Frustration

Definition

An emotional experience occurring in response to perceived obstacles or repeated setbacks, often leading to feelings of helplessness, irritation, or dissatisfaction. Frustration can result from unmet expectations, a lack of progress, or feeling blocked from achieving a goal. This emotion often prompts individuals to reconsider their strategies or goals, potentially reinforcing their determination or, conversely, fostering disengagement and disillusionment. PLEDGE Codebook, T. Capelos

How frustration contributes to PLEDGE conceptual framework

Frustration (in politics) can emerge from perceived barriers to justice, equality, or representation, and it can be channelled in divergent ways depending on emotional mechanisms such as EMRes and EMSoS. When repeated frustrations about unachieved goals or systemic failures are channelled through resentment, they can generate resentment, anger, and hatred, with outgroup blame. When frustrations are capitalized by populist, exclusionary, or authoritarian political narratives and leaders that prioritize reclaiming perceived losses over democratic principles, frustration can point to anti-democratic preferences. In these conditions, we expect citizens to support leaders or policies that prioritize and promise retribution or rapid, unilateral change rather than constructive dialogue. This venting of frustrations through resentment can contribute to anti-democratic actions such as suppression of dissent, undermining of institutions, or scapegoating. In the context of resentimentful grievance politics, such outlets will seemingly address the cause of frustrations through polarizing and divisive means.

Frustration can foster pro-democratic engagement when processed through the emotional mechanism of EMSoS. This mechanism shifts the focus from blame to collective support and empathy, encouraging individuals to share the frustrations originating from grievances in ways that emphasize common experiences and mutual understanding. When frustration is directed through EMSoS toward building connections with peers, and organizing around shared (painful) emotional experiences and goals, it can galvanize collective action and participatory democracy. This channelling of frustrations via EMSoS is envisioned to facilitate dialogue, political advocacy, and reform-oriented movements, as seen in social movements that prioritize systemic change through democratic means rather than polarizing rhetoric. In

the context of solidarity-oriented sharing, frustration can generate resilience and collective empowerment, constructive engagement rather than disengagement.

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3.5 Output Emotions of EMs

3.5.1 Resentment

Definition

Moral anger in response to an intentional and harmful moral or political injustice or wrongdoing that bears on the subject's self-worth. Resentment is felt from singular (I) or plural (we) first-person perspective, and it involves a motivation to punish based on a desire to revenge (Aeschbach, 2017). Resentment is the negative reactive attitude that a person develops in the face of another person's intentional indifference, insult and injury towards him (Strawson, 1974, p. 7, 14).

How resentment contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Resentment has two faces for PLEDGE: a) in the context of pro-democratic grievance politics, it is geared at voicing wrongdoings and it motivates constructive political action to correct or retribute the relevant injustice or wrongdoing with the purpose of emancipating from the victim position; b) in the context of anti-democratic grievance politics, it is geared at claiming victim status and moral superiority as being harmed by some outgroup or -groups, identified as enemies of the self or one's group, and it motives rumination of wrongdoings to oneself and one's victimhood as well as disruptive and violent political action, or support for such action with revenge taken on the object in thought rather than in action. PLEDGE argues that

there are two significantly different types of resentment with dissimilar a) socio-psychological dynamics, b) affective-intentional structure, c) epistemic and normative appropriateness, and d) political consequences, depending on whether resentment emerges spontaneously in response to an injustice or wrong, or by being elicited through the EM Solidarity-Oriented Sharing, or whether it emerges through the EM Ressentiment.

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3.5.1b Indignation

Definition

Moral anger felt from the third-person perspective in response to impersonal wrongs or breaches of norms whose punishment is based on a desire for repairing or restoring the social or moral order disrupted by the offence by third-person retribution or punishment (Aeschbach, 2017; Drummond, 2017).

How indignation contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Indignation is relevant to PLEDGE in relation to EM Ressentiment (EMRes). In EMRes, the frustration and threat to self-worth experienced after repeated failures as envy, shame, humiliation, inefficacious anger, marked by powerlessness and inferiority transform into felt resentment, indignation, contempt, and hatred, directed towards outgroups.

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3.5.2 Hatred

Definition

A deep, enduring, intense emotion expressing animosity, anger and hostility towards a person, group or object" (Reber & Reber, 2002, p. 315).

How hatred contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

PLEDGE identifies hatred as one of the anti-democratic expressions of grievance politics, together with contempt (PLEDGE, Section 1.1.1). In the conceptual framework of PLEDGE, hatred is an outcome emotion of EMRes which does not have anti- and pro-democratic variants like resentment and indignation. EMRes provides an explanation for the blurred focus of hatred and its shifting targets found in extant research (Szanto, 2020). Since hatred emerges through the repression of self-targeting negative emotions such as shame, envy, humiliation, and inefficacious anger, the focus of hatred is blurred from the outset, and it latches onto available targets that easily shift as there is a need to maintain this emotion to keep the driver emotions of resentment repressed. Hatred as a collective political emotion helps us to better understand the rise in patriotism, nationalism, nativism, ethnic group identification and collective narcissism expressed in grievance politics. Intergroup hate speech is commonly adopted in the political use of social media being part and parcel of grievance politics. PLEDGE notes the role of hatred in and out of Ukraine, Russia and European publics during the current war (PLEDGE, Section 1.2.1.3).

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3.5.3 Hope

Definition

A complex, future oriented and rather stable emotion (sentiment) which involves felt anticipation that a desired and morally acceptable outcome is neither impossible nor certain (Ben-Ze'ev, 2000, pp. 475-776; TenHouten, 2007, pp. 224-226; Averill et al., 1990; Averill, 1996; Milona et al., 2025, pp. 218-231; Snyder, 2000; Bal-Tar et al., 2007, p. 449).

Neighbouring concepts

Optimism, Aspiration, Faith, Resilience

How hope contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Hope features in PLEDGE as a key emotion in pro-democratic grievance politics. Hope is central to the emotional mechanism of Solidarity-oriented sharing (EMSoS). EMSoS transforms feelings of frustration and inefficacy into hope, when grievances are shared. Hope helps to turn grievances into pro-democratic political action, encouraging collaboration and deliberation.

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3.5.4 Despair

Definition

Despair is the loss of a ground of hope as such (Steinbock, 2014, p. 189; Steinbock, 2007).

How despair contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Through its association with low self-esteem, reduced efficacy, grief, sadness, and shame, despair belongs to the eliciting conditions of EMRes. To quote Scheler, resentment emerges in “lasting situations which are felt to be ‘injurious’ beyond one’s control – in other words, the more the injury is experienced as a destiny” (Scheler 1961, p. 8). The experience of destiny is close to despair. Despair is a crucial constituent of the emotionality of grievance politics; it can discourage democratic accountability and feed apathy and weaken social and political trust.

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3.5.5 Contempt

Definition

Contempt is an (individual or group-based) emotional response to the appraisal of a person (or a group) as inherently unworthy, involving feelings of being superior, and associated with readiness to exclude the target (Scarantino, 2024, p. 6).

How contempt contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

The PLEDGE proposal notes that in EMRes the frustration and threat to self-worth experienced after repeated failures as envy, shame, humiliation, inefficacious anger, marked by powerlessness and inferiority transform into felt contempt directed towards outgroups (PLEDGE, Section 1.2.1.1). Individuals who experience victimhood and powerlessness, felt as contempt, following historical traumas, adopt reactionist stances with self-victimization narratives (PLEDGE, Section 1.2.1.2).

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3.5.6 Pride

Definition

“Pride is the consequence of a successful evaluation of a specific action. The phenomenological experience is joy over an action, thought or feeling well done” (Lewis, 2016, p. 805).

“A positive emotional response reflecting satisfaction and self-worth, often resulting from personal achievements or the accomplishments of one’s group. It involves feelings of dignity and fulfillment.” (PLEDGE Codebook , T. Capelos).

How pride contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Pride is positively associated with joy and self-esteem (PLEDGE, Section 1.2.1) and negatively with shame. Therefore, PLEDGE expects to find pride in association with EMSoS rather than EMRes. Pride is associated with “empowerment” or “feeling empowered to express one’s social identity” in Social Identity Theory. The connection between pride and concepts such as collective memory has not been fully explored but is relevant socially and politically when groups evoke past successes through remembrance processes and practices (that can become collective nostalgia especially when there is no possibility of reinstantiating a desired past in the present). Group-based positive memories are often described by people when talking about desired or actual achievements in the present and connections or comparisons made with experiences of past group “glories”, although these occasions may also manifest collective hubris (see entry on collective pride/hubris)

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3.5.7 Nostalgia

Definition

“Pleasure and sadness that is caused by remembering something from the past and wishing that you could experience it again” (<https://www.britannica.com/dictionary/nostalgia>).

“The longing for “reintegration of familiarity and spatial-temporal continuity” (Trigg, 2018, p. 49)

Neighbouring concepts

Hope, reactionism, conservatism

How nostalgia contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Individual nostalgia, centered on personal memories, provides a sense of comfort or identity through a longing for one’s own past experiences. Politically, this form of nostalgia intersects with grievance politics, influencing attitudes and behaviors in complex ways. While collective nostalgia (see entry) often drives broader societal narratives, individual nostalgia operates at the personal level, reflecting unique emotional relationships with the past that can either reinforce reactionary stances or foster critical engagement. The PLEDGE framework offers insight into these dynamics, particularly the distinction between restorative and reflective nostalgia (Boym, 2002). Restorative nostalgia, which emphasizes returning to a perceived idealized past, can align with reactionary sentiments, fostering grievances and exclusionary ideologies. This form of nostalgia has been linked to the emotionality of populist rhetoric, particularly in its use as a tool for constructing antagonistic narratives against perceived enemies (Capelos et al., 2024). On the other hand, reflective nostalgia encourages a contemplative and critical engagement with the past. By acknowledging change and complexity, it has the potential to promote learning from history and support pro-democratic political discourse.

Through its investigation of individual-level nostalgia, PLEDGE seeks to understand how personal memories influence political engagement. This includes analyzing nostalgia’s dual role—fueling reactionary politics when leveraged in grievance-based narratives, but also fostering constructive dialogue when approached reflectively. The consortium also explores how individual nostalgia is amplified in the digital age, particularly through social media, as a rhetorical device in populist movements (PLEDGE, Section 1.2.4; Szabo & Kiss, 2021). By examining these intricate dynamics, PLEDGE contributes to a nuanced understanding of how individual nostalgia impacts political attitudes and behaviors, with implications for strengthening democratic values and practices.

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3.5.8 Guilt

Definition

Guilt is a self-conscious moral emotion characterized by the appraisal of having done or thought something specific that is socially wrong and unacceptable. (see: APA Dictionary of Psychology)

Neighbouring concept

Shame

How guilt contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Guilt-proneness relates prosociality as guilt-prone people are more likely to act prosocially or prefer prosocial policies and practises (Cohen et al., 2012). Therefore, PLEDGE expects to find correlation between guilt and the prosocial emotional mechanism of EMSoS. Guilt can also be studied in leadership and political communication (news media and social media of EP2024): guiltling [i.e. guilt ascription to others] and scapegoating as rhetorical strategies are occasionally used to convince the audience about the communicator's moral superiority in contrast to the opponent (Douglas, 1995). In these contexts, guiltling can also relate to EMRes whose characteristics include other-blame and moral righteousness. PLEDGE posits that grievance politics addresses issues that deeply matter to people, encompassing their values, desires, needs, and concerns (Szanto & Slaby, 2020). Recognizing and addressing grievances has the potential to drive positive social change, empowering 'critical citizens' (Norris, 1999)

to engage in a politics of community-building and collective identity (Mouffe, 2016; Palonen, 2020; Vulović & Palonen, 2023).

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3.5.9 Happiness

Definition

A person's evaluation of his or her life in terms of satisfaction judgments and emotional responses, with high subjective well-being associated with high life satisfaction, satisfaction with various life domains, frequent positive affect, and infrequent negative affect (Diener and Sim, 2025).

Neighbouring concepts

Joy

How happiness contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Happiness is the most general long term positive emotion (sentiment) which consists not just in a transient pleasant feeling but in a person's overall evaluation of her life in terms of background framework and, consequently, in terms of both affective and cognitive experiences and evaluations (Diener & Sim, 2024, p. 203; Ben-Ze'ev, 2000, pp. 450-466; Ten Houten, 2007, pp. 31-37). Happiness is tied to hope, gratitude, contentment, and joy, and is experienced after an accomplishment central to one's concern is

consummated (Summa, 2020, p. 421). In this sense, happiness is not the result of an isolated achievement but an ongoing dynamic process (Ben-Ze'ev, 2000, p. 456). In sociological and psychological literature a crucial distinction is between happiness as a feeling or affect (subjective happiness) and happiness as objectively doing well (Averill & More, 2000; Diener & Sim, 2024). In PLEDGE we adopt the "subjective well-being" approach which aims to represent the individuals' experience and determinants of happiness. This experience is highly shaped by the neoliberal feeling rules and/or the emotional regime of wellness and life coaching (McKenzie, 2024; Ahmed, 2010). Happiness is conceptualized in PLEDGE also as one of the emotions that can be engendered by design features of deliberative practices (Morrell et al., 2022; Morrell, 2013).

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3.5.10 Joy

Definition

Joy is a basic, self-directed emotion elicited by a positive evaluation of one's present situation experienced as pleasure or satisfaction from something one desires (Ben-Ze'ev, 2000, p. 72, 507), or from receiving benefits and advantages from others especially when these go beyond what is usual, normative or legitimately expected (Kemper, 2002, p. 67).

Neighbouring concepts

Happiness, enthusiasm

How joy contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

In PLEDGE, joy is categorized alongside other positive emotions, such as gratitude and empathy, that can promote pro-democratic actions. We also expect that joy is experienced when EMSoS is consummated.

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3.5.11 Gratitude

Definition

An emotional response to the appraisal of a received benefit, involving pleasant feelings of appreciation and thankfulness, and associated with readiness to connect more closely to the benefactor (Scarantino, 2024, p. 11).

Gratitude is a positive emotion one feels with the receipt of a gift from another person or entity, i.e., a higher power (DeSteno et al., 2016, p. 835).

How gratitude contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

The concept of gratitude is discussed in PLEDGE as part of the broader range of positive emotions that can promote pro-democratic expression of grievances and constructive political actions. It is grouped together with empathy, solidarity, trust, relevant in EMSoS and in transformations from EMRes to EMSoS.

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3.5.12 Empathy

Definition

“An affective response that stems from the apprehension or comprehension of another’s emotional state or condition, and that is identical or very similar to what the other person is feeling or would be expected to feel” (Eisenberg, 2004, p. 677).

“Empathy is the ability and tendency to share and understand others’ internal states” (Zaki & Ochsner, 2018, p. 871).

Neighbouring concepts

Sympathy, compassion, altruism

How empathy contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

PLEDGE understands empathy not just as an individual emotional response but also as one of the potential antidotes to the divisive and isolating effects of resentment, redirecting it towards pro-social and pro-democratic ends. More analytically, empathy is discussed in PLEDGE as a positive emotion that fosters pro-democratic political action by encouraging individuals to consider and value the perspectives and experiences of others, particularly those who have faced hardships or injustice. Empathy is seen as essential for cultivating democratic values, as it supports inclusivity, social cohesion, and a (collective) sense of responsibility.

Empathy is expected to be absent or very low in the context of EMRes and grievance politics. When individuals focus primarily on their own grievances and perceived injustices, they are consumed by feelings of victimhood, which hinder their ability to empathize with others. This lack of empathy comes together with a narrowed focus on personal or group suffering, often leading to a polarized worldview that sees others as fundamentally different and less deserving of compassion. Individuals in resentment are more likely to seek adversarial or

retaliatory actions and less likely to engage in constructive dialogue or seek mutual understanding. This can create a cycle of division, as individuals and groups become isolated in their grievances, viewing others as opponents or threats rather than fellow members of a shared community. In political contexts, this can manifest as scapegoating, divisive rhetoric, and a rejection of democratic ideals that promote inclusivity and cooperation. Empathy plays a crucial role in the solidarity-oriented sharing of grievances and is envisioned as a key component of EMSoS. When individuals share their experiences of grievances, empathy allows others to connect emotionally with these experiences, facilitating understanding and support. This emotional connection helps to create bonds across different social groups and can lead to a sense of solidarity that motivates collective action. By empathizing with those who feel marginalized or aggrieved, individuals are more likely to engage in actions that promote democratic values, such as justice, equality, and mutual respect.

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3.5.13 Compassion

Definition

“An emotional response to the appraisal of having high coping potential with respect to the suffering of someone relevant and worthy, involving feelings of concern and resonance which are mixed in valence, and associated with readiness to help and understand the sufferer” (Scarantino, 2024, p. 6).

“Compassion is a painful emotion occasioned by the awareness of another person’s undeserved misfortune” (Nussbaum, 2001, p. 301).

“A deep emotional response characterized by a desire to alleviate the suffering of others. It involves recognizing another’s pain and feeling motivated to help them, reflecting a sense of connection and concern for their well-being.” (PLEDGE Codebook, T. Capelos)

Neighbouring concepts

Empathy, sympathy, altruism

How compassion relates to PLEDGE conceptual framework

Since misery is a constant feature of contemporary societies due to socio-economic inequalities and poly-crises, compassion as a transitory emotion can easily turn into long-term sentiment (Ben-Ze’ev 2000: 83) and, thus, it can be reckoned as one key moral sentiment which plays central role in addressing injustices neglected by political elites (Hoggett 2006). Accordingly, PLEDGE expects to find compassion in the context of EMSoS where it can emerge towards fellow in-group members as well as toward out-group members identified as suffering from similar injustice as the in-group. Compassion can also be seen as a political emotion that plays crucial role in the shaping of political cultural climates (Demertzis 2014, 2020). The normative claims of compassionate politics are mainly centered on the inferior-superior relationship which might be covered up while helping others, as well as to the suitability of compassion as a moral-emotional stance to cope with the others’ unjust suffering.

The political relevance of compassion has become salient not only in virtue of “compassion fatigue” caused by the over-exposure to mediatised suffering of distant others (Demertzis 2020: 80; Garber 2004: 19-20) but also due to divergent public moralities through which compassion is being used in political discourse and practice. On one hand, by keeping socio-economic distances and inequalities intact, compassionate conservatism reduces compassion to charity and masculinized patronage blaming sufferers for their own misfortune (Woodward 2004); on the other hand, the liberal narrative of compassion is more rationalistic and cognitive than empathetic and it encounters others’ suffering from the point of view of the rational spectator rather than of the embodied compassionate citizen who is able to feel the pain of others and at the same time think critically about social injustice (Woodward 2004: 68; Hoggett 2006: 160-161). PLEDGE aims to develop and reinforce this kind of embodied compassion in its innovations of democratic governance and emotionally sensitive communication.

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3.5.14 Disgust

Definition

“Disgust is a strong sense of aversion to something perceived as capable of contaminating us: either in physical terms, referring to bodily infection, or in more symbolic terms, referring to violating the boundaries of self” (Ben-Ze’ev, 2000, p. 387).

“An emotional response to what is appraised as pathogenic, as an inappropriate sexual partner, or as a moral violation, involving feelings of literal or figurative contamination, with motivations to avoid proximity and contact and to expel” (Scarantino, 2024, p. 7).

Neighbouring concept

Contempt

How disgust contributes to PLEDGE conceptual framework

In the social realm, disgust is directed at an agent as a whole and not at specific actions of agents (Ben-Ze’ev, 2000, p. 98, 111, 379). An object of disgust is perceived as repulsive even

if it has not or may not inflict any harm to the subject of disgust. Also, unlike contempt, disgust is irrelevant with inequality or social superiority. It poses protective boundaries of the self to avoid contamination in a sharp and immediate manner here and now. Vindicating its defensive nature, disgust has been found to correlate positively with social and political conservatism, low self-esteem, and neuroticism, while it is negatively correlated with openness to experience in the Big Five personality traits inventory. It is also linked with right-wing authoritarianism, social dominance orientation, religious fundamentalism, violent intergroup conflict, hate speech and dehumanization (Rozin et al., 2016, p. 825, 827). Repulsive and revulsive dehumanization refers mainly to intergroup relations (Hodson et al., 2013). Emanating from ingroup perceived superiority and purity, outgroups can be considered as physically and culturally “pollutants” who threaten ingroup’s wellbeing, norms, and values. Accordingly, PLEDGE expects to find disgust in the context of EMRes as an outcome emotion felt towards blamed-for outgroups, together with contempt.

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3.5.15 Enthusiasm

Definition

“An emotional response prompted by an anticipated or immediate reward involving pleasant feelings of anticipation and eagerness, with strong motivation and high readiness to act” (Scarantino 2024, p. 9).

Neighbouring concepts

Joy, happiness

How enthusiasm contributes to PLEDGE conceptual framework

PLEDGE expects to find enthusiasm in the context of EMSoS where it associates with hope and optimism in achieving political change with constructive, purposive collective action with peer others. Due to its strong motivational potential, enthusiasm is usually correlated with intense political interest and political participation; also associated with EMSoS in PLEDGE conceptual framework. Yet enthusiasm can be misapplied also by populist authoritarian leaders to cultivate fanaticism among their followers.

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3.5.16 Sadness

Definition

“An emotional response to the appraisal of low coping potential with respect to an obstructed goal of high importance, involving unpleasant feelings of loss, and associated with readiness to disengage from physical interactions with the world plus readiness for increased self-reflection” (Scarantino 2024, p. 16).

Neighbouring concepts

Frustration

How sadness contributes to PLEDGE conceptual framework

Although neither sadness nor grief or sorrow are mentioned in PLEDGE proposal, sadness will be measured in Activities 4.1.1 and 4.2.2 (longitudinal survey) since it is center staged in the emotional dynamics of grievance politics. Based on perceived maltreatment and injustices, grievances do not only evoke other-directed negative emotions like anger and hatred, but also self-directed emotions negatively valenced, such as sadness.

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3.5.17 Disappointment

Definition

Disappointment is a secondary negative emotion composed by sadness and surprise (Ten Houten, 2007, p. 47, 73); it is felt when one feels depressingly surprised that something that one anticipated, went for, or planned does not materialize.

Neighbouring concepts

Frustration, sadness

How disappointment contributes to PLEDGE conceptual framework

As a rule, the cause of disappointment is other than the self and this is precisely the feature that renders it unexpected. In this respect, disappointment is a counterfactual emotion generated by the appraisal of what might have happened but didn't (Elster, 1999, p. 241). Besides, the more important the goal is for the agent the more intense disappointment will be felt which might culminate in resignation or even in grief. Schimmack and Diener (1997) provided evidence that disappointment is the third most frequently experienced negative emotion after anxiety and anger. Sociologically, this is because contemporary society is prone to anomy and frustration since it raises expectations by cultivating positive thinking standards depriving at the same time millions of people the means to live up to these expectations. More than so as a near success is more frustrating and disappointment is stronger when one imagines oneself within close reach of a desired and morally valued goal (Ben-Ze'ev, 2000, p. 21-22). PLEDGE hypothesises that the neoliberal societal conditions, where individuals are by default blamed for their failures and misfortunes, are prone to motivate transformation of disappointment into envy, shame, humiliation, or inefficacious anger that breed resentment.

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3.5.18 Optimism

Definition

Optimism is a positive secondary emotion consisting of the combination of anticipation with joy (TenHouten, 2007, pp. 73-75). The opposite of optimism is pessimism which is a combination of anticipation and sadness.

Neighbouring concept

Hope

How optimism contributes to PLEDGE conceptual framework

Optimism when experienced through resentment, will manifest as an expectation for change in a way that singles out a perceived adversary or group as responsible for societal grievances. This “hope” for rectification will be hostage to the original grievance and will be conditional upon the displacement of the original self identity and its values. In this sense, the version of optimism through resentment nurtures a vision for the future that remains antagonistic, where the positive outcome is at the expense of others, seen as their undoing or defeat, much akin to schadenfreude.

Optimism channeled through solidarity-oriented sharing fosters collective hope not at the expense of others but through common goals, and aligning with notions of democratic participation and social cohesion. This type of optimism emphasizes mutual empowerment and relies on shared steps to create an improved future. In contexts of solidarity, optimism becomes a positive, energizing force that motivates collective action, resilience, and cooperation to achieve positive societal change. Here the focus is on progress towards shared goals rather than division. It is also envisaged through the EMSoS disappointment about past failures or misfortunes can change into optimism and despair into hope.

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3.6 Psychological Triggers and Facilitators of EMs

Psychological triggers refer to underlying psychological factors that, alongside emotional mechanisms, shape how individuals and groups respond to political and social grievances and challenges. This section highlights how these triggers—including emotional needs, trust and distrust, cynicism and kynicism, emotional climate, collective pride and hubris, and collective nostalgia—play distinct roles in reinforcing or weakening tendencies toward resentment or solidarity. They influence whether individuals and groups engage with one another through antagonism or mutual support. For example, trust can foster solidarity by strengthening group identity, while distrust may fuel resentment by amplifying perceived threats

3.6.1 Emotional needs

Definition

Emotional needs refer to the fundamental psychological requirements that individuals seek to fulfil in their interpersonal interactions and social environments. These encompass a range such as the need for validation, recognition, empathy, and belonging. When unaddressed, emotional needs can lead to feelings of frustration, anger, and give rise to grievances, significantly influencing individuals' behaviour and attitudes toward political systems and institutions.

How emotional needs contribute to PLEDGE conceptual framework

PLEDGE focuses on emotional needs to understand how policies that address or sidestep them influence political engagement and decision-making processes in contemporary democracies. For this, PLEDGE studies policymaking approaches and practices. While policymakers have become increasingly aware of the emotional context surrounding political decision-making in recent years, the "loud and uncivil" emotionality of anti-democratic grievance politics heightens the stakes associated with recognizing and addressing emotional needs within the policy landscape (Kaur & Sharma, 2017). Civil servants, traditionally trained to maintain a dispassionate stance, are now recognizing that unaddressed grievances can trigger further discontent, compromise communication with the public, and erode political trust. This cycle is often referred to as the "endless negative spiral of chronic grievance" (Kaya, 2019, 2021; Droste, 2021).

In situations where tensions run high, elected officials may find themselves "captured" by the emotional needs of "angry voters" or influenced by groupthink dynamics. These officials can also be pressured by authoritarian figures or demagogues who exploit grievances for political gain. Additionally, media organizations may amplify grievances for financial profit. Understanding how citizens' emotional needs and the dynamics of emotional interactions between policy actors shape policymaking processes in the context of grievance politics is crucial. PLEDGE studies emotional needs of citizens to identify the key challenges policymakers face in navigating the emotional economy of grievance politics, with a particular focus on the gaps in communication and decision-making practices between different policy actors and the public. PLEDGE also explores successful strategies that policy actors have adopted to address the emotional needs of citizens across various crises.

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3.6.2 Trust

Definition

Trust is a positive tertiary emotion or sentiment composed of anticipation, acceptance and joy, which in post-traditional societies facilitates one's cooperation with other people or institutions where one, based on inconclusive evidence, freely expects that another's actions will not be detrimental and/or will be in favor to one's wishes and interests with regards to certain domains and within a relatively long-time span (Demertzis, 2017, 2006).

Trust differs from basic emotions in that it is more complex and involves cognitive elements such as expectation and anticipation. While basic emotions like fear or happiness are immediate, instinctual reactions to stimuli, trust is a reflective, social sentiment that develops over time.

Neighbouring concepts

Confidence, Political Trust, Political Satisfaction, Distrust, Political Disaffection

How trust contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

PLEDGE argues that grievance politics, whether in its democratic or anti-democratic form, emerges in part from the erosion of generalized social trust in contemporary Western societies. When the social fabric fractures, cooperation is disturbed, and the routines of public life are disarranged bringing about anxiety and normative disorientation. Under these terms, the needs of citizens with low social trust for ontological/existential security renders them vulnerable to demagogic rhetoric and fake news consumption. Social trust/distrust is a pivotal concept in PLEDGE as trust and its opposite are almost omnipresent throughout the project proposal (e.g., WP1, WP4, WP5, WP7) since it "regulates", as it were, the dynamics of the emotional economy of grievance politics. In that sense trust/distrust, in tandem with cynicism, makes for the broader emotional climate where grievances articulate as a political force.

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3.6.3 Cynicism/Kynicism

Definition

(Political) cynicism is a cluster political emotion or sentiment which consists of a number of interwoven negative feelings and cognitions such as melancholy, pessimism, latent desperation, irony, self-pity, hopelessness, scepticism, sarcasm, guffaw, mocking, cheering, aloofness, distrust, mistrust, misanthropism, blasé relativism, bad faith, fatalism, nihilism, discontent, indignation, resentment, resignation, and powerlessness. (Demertzis, 2014, 2020)

Neighbouring concepts

Skepticism, alienation, grievance

How cynicism/kynicism contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

The cynicism/kynicism distinction is relevant for the examination of the democratic potential of grievance politics. In PLEDGE, kynicism captures the mixture of considerations occurring under healthy scepticism, political distrust and plebeian scorn and would be expected under the pro-democratic expressions of grievance politics. Cynicism is the nihilistic counter-democratic posture, which is negatively related to trust as described PLEDGE in the section on the psychological triggers and facilitators of EM's, and it is expected to be present in anti-democratic expressions of grievances.

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3.6.4 Emotional climate

Definition

Emotional climate is a way the people of a society emotionally relate to one another through predominant collective emotions generated by the social interaction of a group's members in a particular milieu (de Rivera, 1992; de Rivera & Paez, 2007).

Neighbouring concepts

Feeling rules, collective emotions, social sharing

How emotional climate contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

The concept of “emotional climate” is not mentioned explicitly in the conceptual and framework of PLEDGE. However, PLEDGE studies emotional climates by examining circulation and transformation of collective emotions in real and digital/virtual environments and how these emotions are exploited in anti-democratic grievance politics, as well as feeling rules that indirectly relate to emotional atmospheres in communities and societies.

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3.6.5 Collective pride/hubris

Definition

Collective pride involves a shared sense of accomplishment, unity, or superiority, often manifesting during events like celebrations, responses to crises, or in situations of intergroup competition. Collective hubris, instead, is a form of excessive pride, that may emerge as an overconfidence in the group's abilities or entitlements, leading to potentially unrestrained or aggressive actions towards outgroups (Salmela & Sullivan, 2022; Sullivan & Day, 2019).

How collective pride/hubris contribute to PLEDGE conceptual framework

Collective pride is a positive evaluation and feeling about an important or salient in-group which, when felt widely and genuinely by “psychological groups” such as political party supporters, nation states or members of cross-national solidarity movements, can have

impacts such as believing one's group is valuable and result in greater feelings of well-being, optimism about the group's future, group confidence about subsequent actions.

In collective hubris, an achievement of one's group has a merely causal and contingent role as evidence for the group's greatness and superiority which is the constitutive appraisal of this emotion (Sullivan & Hollway, 2014). Thus, collective hubris manifests as overconfidence in continued success in organizations, corporations, or sports teams. Besides appraisals of the group's greatness and superiority, collective hubris involves expressions that differ in kind from collective pride in being arrogant and antagonistic toward competitors and other group(s) that are perceived as denying or doubting or challenging the privileged status of the in-group (Sullivan, 2017). In this understanding of collective hubris, beliefs of the group's greatness or superiority, together with expressions of arrogant boasting and negative collective and group-based emotions such as contempt and anger with underlying shame replace rather than extend collective pride, which is a positive celebratory emotion about particular achievements of one's group (Sullivan & Hollway, 2014; Sullivan & Day, 2019). The sense that one's group is believed and felt to be special in collective hubris is captured better by the notion of collective narcissism (de Zavala et al., 2009) than by collective pride.

PLEDGE hypothesises collective pride to associate with groups operating on EMSoS emerging in the groups' collective demonstrations and actions for their shared goals, whereas we expect to find collective hubris from groups operating on EMRes where it associates with reclaiming the lost greatness of the group.

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3.6.6 Collective nostalgia

Definition

“Collective nostalgia is a bittersweet emotion that reflects sentimental longing for valued aspects of the past of one’s group” (Stefaniak et al., 2021).

How collective nostalgia contributes to PLEDGE conceptual framework

In contrast to individual nostalgia which focuses on personal memories, offering a sense of comfort or identity rooted in the past, collective nostalgia emerges from shared experiences or histories, uniting groups around a common idealized past. This collective longing is particularly significant in populist politics, where it often manifests in restorative forms, framing the past as a golden age disrupted by external forces such as globalization or modernization. Collective restorative nostalgia amplifies group identity, creating clear boundaries between "us" and "them" (Boym, 2002; Demertzis, 2020). It serves as a powerful mobilizing force in populist movements, fueling grievances and reactionary politics by casting perceived outsiders or elites as threats. The PLEDGE framework investigates these dynamics further, emphasizing how collective nostalgia interlinks with reactionism and grievance-based narratives. This contrasts with reflective nostalgia, which acknowledges the past critically and can foster pro-democratic engagement by promoting dialogue between historical perspectives and present challenges. As noted by Szabo & Kiss (2021), social media amplifies the use of restorative nostalgia in populist discourse, illustrating its role as a rhetorical tool in shaping political attitudes and behaviors. By examining the contrasts between individual and collective nostalgia and their implications for politics, we gain insight into how collective longing for an idealized past can both unify and polarize societies, particularly within the context of populist movements.

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3.7 Ideological and Psychological Orientations & Mind States

EMRes and EMSoS offer valuable insights into the relationship between left-right ideologies and anti-democratic tendencies, which have traditionally been associated with conservative and right-wing perspectives (Jost et al., 2017). Cross-national studies reveal that a conspiracy mentality can manifest at both ends of the political spectrum (Bilewicz & Imhoff, 2022). For instance, reactionary stances linked to EMRes have been shown to predict leftist politics in Greece and rightist politics in the UK (Capelos & Demertzis, 2022; Capelos et al., 2023).

A key contrast exists between social dominance orientation (SDO)—an ideology that legitimizes inequality and views the political landscape as a jungle—and right-wing authoritarianism (RWA), which emphasizes conventionalism, obedience, aggression, and a perception of the world as dangerous. While both ideologies reside on the political right (Duckitt & Sibley, 2009), they exhibit opposing effects on issues such as hate speech acceptance (Bilewicz et al., 2017) and vaccination hesitancy (Bilewicz & Soral, 2022). In contexts of perceived threat, RWA tends to predict compliance with government policies, whereas SDO often leads to non-compliance.

The question remains whether the compliance exhibited by RWA adherents is driven by pro-democratic or anti-democratic motivations, even as their actions align with government recommendations. This ambiguity suggests that the emotional underpinnings of ideological orientations may play a crucial role in shaping political preferences. By employing the EM typology, PLEDGE maps the motivations behind the differing policy preferences of RWA and SDO adherents, concentrating on the emotional needs that drive these orientations. This understanding could lead to more effective policymaking that addresses the distinct emotional needs of individuals with high RWA or high SDO.

3.7.1 Authoritarianism

Definition

‘Authoritarianism is approached in the literature as a stable personality structure, ideology, or ideological attitude based on conventionalism, obedience, and aggression, and the perception of the world as a dangerous place’ (Capelos et al., 2024). Although authoritarianism is often associated with right-wing politics, studies in political psychology show that authoritarianism can be present across the ideological spectrum, each tailored to fit the underlying beliefs and values of the left or right (for more on the similarities and differences between right and left wing authoritarianism see Conway et al., 2018 and Costello et al., 2022). Authoritarianism regardless of its left or right orientation implies a firm and life-long outlook towards how the world should be and emphasises conformity and intolerance towards dissenting opinions. Individuals on both the right and the left are inclined to support authoritarian measures under different ideological justifications.

How authoritarianism contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Right-wing authoritarianism is associated with conservative ideologies and has been identified as a strong predictor of right-wing populist attitudes. Left-wing authoritarianism is characterised by rigid adherence to ideological purity and strong desire to punish those opposed to its strong ideals to equality and social justice (Duckitt, 1989; Feldman, 2003; Weyland, 2018; Sauer, 2020; Enyedi, 2020; Osbourne et al., 2023; Conway et al., 2018).

Authoritarianism, particularly right-wing authoritarianism, is discussed as an ideological orientation and a psychological trigger that is conducive to EMRes as it facilitates hierarchical and rigid structures that can intensify feelings of personal and social frustration and grievance. At the individual level, authoritarian attitudes denote the tendency to submit to authority, adhere to social conventions and is associated with aggression towards outgroups. This mentality can therefore serve as a psychological environment that can promote the input emotions of EMRes, as individuals can feel marginalized or suppressed. Turning to output emotions, authoritarianism tends to encourage individuals to displace frustration towards blaming scapegoats. The desire to elevate one’s group, to redirect grievances towards outgroups, and foster a collective sense of victimhood, are common elements between authoritarianism and EMRes (Capelos et al., 2024).

Authoritarianism is discussed in PLEDGE in relation to social dominance orientation (SDO) and right-wing authoritarianism (RWA), as lenses for understanding how different right-wing ideological orientations shape political behavior.

Authoritarianism is also relevant in PLEDGE in relation to the emotional dynamics of grievance politics, in contexts where authoritarian leaders exploit antagonistic discourses and feelings of fear, anger, frustration, and a sense of injustice and insecurity.

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3.7.2 Reactionism

Definition

Reactionism is a psychological orientation which denotes the "desire for urgent uprooting of the present and the need to restore the past (Capelos & Katsanidou, 2018; Wolfe, 1923).

How reactionism contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

In PLEDGE, reactionism is theorized as a political orientation which consolidates the desire to abruptly and urgently change the present to reinstate an idealised past. It is expressed as anti-preferences, dogmatic thinking, and it is founded on retrospective values that favour tradition and security and oppose stimulation and new experiences (Capelos et al., 2024). This orientation has been found to predict anti-democratic and anomic actions (Capelos & Demertzis, 2022), as those who hold reactionary views often seek to urgently dismantle contemporary systems they view as corrupt or threatening to traditional values (PLEDGE, p.124). Alongside resentment and collective narcissism, reactionism forms what Capelos et al. (2024) describe as the "anti-social triad" of grievance politics, a set of emotional and cognitive dispositions that drive conflictual, divisive, and destabilizing political behaviors.

Moreover, reactionism plays a central role in the emotional economy of grievance politics explored in PLEDGE, particularly in relation to EMRes, which is linked to both left- and right-wing reactionary politics. EMRes is key in explaining how grievances are emotionally experienced, mobilized, and circulated in ways that can foster resistance to progressive change and fuel populist movements across the political spectrum. In the PLEDGE conceptual framework, reactionism emerges as a significant factor in shaping contemporary political landscapes through its deep-rooted emotional attachment to past ideals and their politics.

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3.7.3 Individual and Collective Narcissism

Definition

Narcissism is a psychological construct approached as “a psychological/mental state denoting affection for a collective entity, while simultaneously concealing a deeper injury of (personal and collective) ego-strength and an anxious, disintegrated self” (Capelos et al., 2024, p. 5).

Collective narcissism is “marked by (a) the rejection of the value of external groups, and (b) an unrealized, anxious distrust in one’s own group and its fellow members” (Capelos et al., 2024, p.7).

How individual and collective narcissism contribute to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

In PLEDGE, collective narcissism plays a significant role in understanding the emotional mechanisms (EMs) that help explaining grievance politics. Collective narcissism refers to a group-level psychological state of mind in which members of a group hold an inflated belief in the superiority or exceptionalism of their group, while at the same time being highly sensitive to perceived disrespect or criticism from others (de Zavala et al., 2009), because of the active repression of shame (Capelos et al., 2024). The collective sense of grandiosity in collective narcissism is fragile and easily threatened, always contrasted, and therefore dependent on the inferiority of an outgroup, and leads to defensive and often aggressive responses when the group feels its status is under attack.

Within the PLEDGE framework, collective narcissism forms part of what Capelos et al. (2024) refer to as the "anti-social triad of grievance politics," alongside reactionism and resentment. Collective narcissism is strengthened by and in turn strengthens the climate of social and political polarization, where groups prioritize defending their perceived superiority, and because they do not recognize the value of other groups, they are unlikely to engage in democratic dialogue and cooperation. According to Capelos et al. 2024 “collective narcissism goes hand in hand with negative emotionality, lack of self-appreciation, and deficits in gratitude, compassion and social connectedness” (p. 8) which is compensated by intergroup distrust, antagonism, and conspiratorial thinking (de Zavala, 2009).

Collective narcissism is particularly relevant to EMRes. It is expected to surface during the consolidating stage of this mechanism, and present alongside feelings of resentment, outgroup hostility, and moral superiority. This emotional state of mind amplifies the desire to depersonalize and even punish out-groups, and even dissenting voices which are internal to the group, therefore undermining democratic norms and exacerbating polarization. In this context, collective narcissism drives exclusionary and antagonistic political behaviors, often framed around victimhood narratives and perceived threats to group identity.

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3.7.4 Social Dominance Orientation

Definition

Social Dominance Orientation (SDO) is a psychological construct that refers to an orientation that signifies preference for hierarchy within social groups and the belief that some groups should dominate others. This guiding framework shows support for group-based inequality and may endorse prejudiced attitudes towards outgroups. Therefore, SDO is primarily measured using scales that assess attitudes toward social hierarchies and group relations (Pratto et al., 1994).

Neighbouring concepts

Authoritarianism, reactionism, prejudice

How SDO contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

PLEDGE contrasts SDO with authoritarianism, as well as right-wing authoritarianism (RWA). Studies show that like RWA, SDO traditionally sits on the right of the political spectrum and is more commonly associated with conservative ideologies. There are some cases where left-wing political preferences align with high SDO, but this is only in contexts where the left prioritizes in-group dominance or hierarchy (Feldman & Stenner, 1997; Van Hiel et al., 2006). Studies also show that SDO and RWA have differing impacts on political issues such as hate speech and vaccination hesitancy (Dellagiacoma et al., 2024). In threat-inducing situations, SDO tends to predict non-compliance with government policies. The project aims to use the framework of emotional mechanisms (EMRes and EMSoS) to map the motivations driving the policy preferences of high-SDO individuals.

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3.7.5 Populist Attitudes

Definition

Populist attitudes are predispositions of cognitive and affective nature which predict voting for populist parties (Hawkins et al., 2018).

Neighbouring concepts

Authoritarianism, anti-elitism.

How populist attitudes contribute to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

The significance of populism and populist attitudes draws on extant research of consortia members, e.g. resentment in left and right wing populism (Salmela & Capelos, 2021), survey data analysis driving right wing populism in Germany (Nguyen, Salmela, von Scheve, 2021), ontological insecurity and gendered nationalism (Agius et al., 2020), emotions and populism (Demertzis, 2006), populism and twitter (Herkman & Palonen, 2024), core features of populism (Palonen 2020; Vulović & Palonen 2023), studies on the populist ‘mind’, anxiety, fantasy and everyday populism (Kinnvall & Svensson, 2022), political polarization and populism in Hungary (Palonen, 2009, 2018) and populism in VR environments (Kazlauskaitė, 2022, 2024).

Populism and populist attitudes are discussed in PLEDGE in relation to the study of anti- and pro-democratic grievances across key countries and contexts as well as the development of policy instruments that harness emotional expression in politics for strengthening democracies. Left-wing populism is discussed in the context of the Emotional Mechanism of Solidarity-Oriented Sharing (EMSoS). The proposal notes the value of left-wing populism among peers of collective goals and ingroup solidary bonds.

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3.7.6 Conspiracy mentality

Definition

It has been documented that there is a difference between believing in specific conspiracy theories (e.g., the assassination of JFK) and the more stable inclination to interpret troublesome events in a conspiratorial manner. The latter is called “conspiracy mentality” (Imhoff & Bruder, 2014; Imhoff & Lamberty, 2020) meaning that those who score high on conspiracy mentality scales may not necessarily be hardcore conspiracy theorists (Klein & Nera 2020, p. 130). Further, conspiracy mentality is not restricted to political extremes but is pervasive across social groups and ideological camps (Uscinski & Parent, 2014).

How conspiracy mentality contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

The current conspiracy mentality argument draws from Serge Moscovici’s (1987) analysis of conspiratorial thinking in history where he discerned the existence of a ‘conspiracy mentality’, as a social representation of society consisting of two opposing classes: The evil conspiring “others” and the virtuous, normal, and lawful “us”. As this representation resembles the populist understanding of social antagonism, the link of populism to conspiracy theory has received increased attention in the past two decades (Butter, 2025, p. 4). Empirical research has established a relationship between political distrust, lack of interpersonal trust, and political powerlessness (Jolley & Douglas, 2014), on the one hand, and conspiracy beliefs (Goertzel, 1994); it was also found that one predictor of conspiracy beliefs is collective narcissism (Cichocka et al., 2016), while they and can manifest at both ends of the political spectrum (Bilewicz & Imhoff, 2022) he current conspiracy mentality argument draws directly from Serge Moscovici’s (1987) analysis of conspiratorial thinking in history where he discerned the existence of a ‘conspiracy mentality’, as a social representation of society consisting of two opposing classes: The evil conspiring “others” and the virtuous, normal, and lawful “us”. As this representation resembles the populist understanding of social antagonism, the link of populism to conspiracy theory has received increased attention in the past two decades (Butter, 2025, p. 4). Empirical research has established a relationship between political distrust, lack of interpersonal trust, and political powerlessness (Jolley & Douglas, 2014), on the one hand, and conspiracy beliefs (Goertzel, 1994); it was also found that one predictor of conspiracy beliefs is collective narcissism (Cichocka et al., 2016), while they and can manifest at both ends of the political spectrum (Bilewicz & Imhoff, 2022). On

the basis existing evidence, PLEDGE expects to find conspiratorial mentality to associate with EMRes.

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3.7.7 Political interest

Definition

Political interest or interest in politics is curiosity about politics, or the degree to which politics arouses a citizen's curiosity (Van Deth, 1990, p. 278; Van Deth & Elff, 2000; Van Deth & Elff, 2004; Gabriel & Van Deth, 1995).

How political interest contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Funded by
the European Union

As interest in politics is a strong predictor of political and electoral participation, we will be able to investigate whether and to what extent resentful, cynical, kynical, authoritarian, and reactionary citizens take part in politics across different levels of internal and external political efficacy. In this way we will examine how and why grievances are politicized towards either a democratic or anti-democratic direction.

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3.7.8 Efficacy (political)

Definition

“The feeling that individual political action does and can have impact upon the political process, namely, that it is worthwhile to perform one’s own civic duties” (Campbell et al.,

1954, p. 187). “The feeling that political and social change is possible and that the individual can play a part in bringing about this change” (Campbell et al., 1954, p. 188).

How efficacy contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Efficacy, and political efficacy for that matter, plays a key role in EMSoS because EMSoS starts with inefficacy and transforms it into efficacy, through secure and solidary bonds with in-group others in relation to hopeful expectation that change is possible, when a goal is shared in a like-minded collective. High internal political efficacy is expected to be more correlated with both pro and anti-democratic grievance politics than low external political efficacy. Political internal and external inefficacy fosters the EMRes and is conducive to reactionary political style. (Capelos and Demertzis, 2018).

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3.7.9 Sophistication (political)

Definition

Political sophistication is the level of an individual’s political knowledge, the structure of their political beliefs, and the consistency of their political views. Political sophistication represents

“the extent to which people’s political cognitions are numerous, cut finely, abstract, and systematically interconnected” (Luskin, 1987, p. 857).

How political sophistication contributes to PLEDGE conceptual framework

Political sophistication is conceptualized as the level of structure, depth, and integration in an individual's political beliefs and knowledge. Luskin (1990) defines it as a combination of "political knowledge, political interest, and the organization of political thoughts" (Luskin, 1990, p. 332), emphasizing its role in enabling individuals to make informed and consistent political judgments. Individuals high in political sophistication tend to hold more stable, internally consistent opinions and demonstrate an ability to place political issues within a broader ideological or policy framework (Delli Carpini & Keeter, 1996). Zaller (1992) demonstrates that political sophistication (or awareness) affects how individuals interpret political messages, with those higher in sophistication better able to resist simplistic or manipulative messaging. Accordingly, PLEDGE hypothesises that political sophistication can help shape the intensity and direction of the emotional mechanisms of grievance politics, either delaying resentment or promoting solidarity-oriented sharing. We expect that political sophistication influences how grievances are perceived but also how they are emotionally processed and acted upon.

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3.7.10 Knowledge (political)

Definition

Political knowledge refers to the awareness and understanding individuals possess about political events, processes, institutions, and actors. It encompasses the recognition of names, the comprehension of concepts, and the ability to interpret and analyze political information.

How political knowledge contributes to PLEDGE conceptual framework

Political knowledge is essential for informed civic participation and is often linked to an individual's capacity to engage in political discussions, evaluate political arguments, and make reasoned decisions during elections. PLEDGE expects that political knowledge will be related to how individuals engage with grievance politics. A higher level of political knowledge is expected to equip individuals to navigate complex political landscapes, discern the nuances of social injustices, and articulate their grievances more effectively. As people become more informed about political events, concepts, and the workings of institutions, they are expected to be better positioned to critically evaluate grievances. Research suggests that individuals who are more politically informed tend to respond less emotionally or negatively to political issues. Knowledge can buffer individuals from purely affective or negative reactions in political contexts (Marcus et al., 2000). Therefore, they are expected to be less prone to negative political affectivity. However, we do not expect political knowledge to be directly related to solidarity-oriented sharing. We expect that the connection between political knowledge, emotion, and political action to be moderated by trust and gratitude.

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3.8 Values, Individual and Group Identities, and Political Attachments

PLEDGE draws on insights from social identity theory (Tajfel & Turner, 1979; Turner et al., 1987), which posits that our individual self comprises two components: the personal, which distinguishes us from others, and the social, which delineates our differences from out-groups. Both dimensions of our identity hold significant emotional weight. Groups provide essential sources of belonging, pride, and self-esteem, leading members to strive for a positive differentiation from relevant out-groups. Success in these intergroup comparisons evokes (individual and collective) feelings of pride and joy, while failure can result in shame and humiliation, undermining the security of one's social identity (Mackie & Smith, 2018).

Recent analyses of populist leaders through the lens of social identity theory have identified them as "identity entrepreneurs" (Uysal et al., 2022). However, the specific mechanisms through which the emotionality of grievances is mobilized or transformed remain underexplored (e.g., Haslam et al., 2022, on Trump, active followership, and the storming of the Capitol building).

A pertinent case to consider is Russia, where restoring a secure social identity may necessitate shifts in group values. Research indicates a retreat from European ideals of equality, justice, and modernity—values ingrained during the Soviet era—toward traditional conservatism, nationalism, anti-Western national sentiment, and anti-modernism, with the persecution of sexual minorities and a free press under Putin’s regime. The emerging moral paradigm of a “millennial Russia” as the last bastion of traditional Christian values, allegedly forsaken by the decadent West, serves as a fertile ground for transforming repressed feelings of defeat, shame, and humiliation from the Soviet Union’s collapse into expressed emotions of righteous anger, moral superiority, and hatred (Sharafutdinova, 2020).

Similar trends are observed in recent studies on reactionism across Europe, highlighting a shift from valuing adventure-seeking to respecting tradition and reinstating the past, driven by anger, feelings of inefficacy, and anxiety (Capelos & Katsanidou, 2018; Capelos & Demertzis, 2018, 2022). These findings suggest that our core values—often perceived as stable and resistant to change, typically shifting only through generational transitions (Inglehart & Norris, 2019)—can transform from emancipatory to conservative, materialistic, and nationalistic in response to economic or psychological crises that disrupt our social identities (Scharfbillig et al., 2021; Hochschild, 2016; Salmela & von Scheve, 2017).

These ongoing interactions among emotions, values, and individual and group identities complicate the establishment of universally applicable, one-way causal links. PLEDGE advances extant literature by examining how emotional experiences connected through emotional mechanisms and tied to grievances can produce both anti-democratic and pro-democratic outcomes, while also transforming the values, identities, and emotions of those involved.

3.8.1 Core Values

Definition

Core values are fundamental beliefs that guide individuals' behavior and decision-making processes (Schwartz, 1992). Schwartz identified ten values which are referred to as ‘core’ because they are seen as universally relevant across cultures and essential to understanding motivations and behavior. These values guide actions by fulfilling basic human needs, and they are also therefore referred to as ‘basic human values’.

How core values contribute to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Extant research assumes that values are highly stable at the individual level and they are mostly shaped by life conditions through the influence of parents, neighbours, friends and schools. When values shift at a societal level, the shift is slow and driven by cohort or generational changes (Inglehart & Norris, 2019; Scharfbillig et al., 2021). PLEDGE argues that the recent rise of anti-democratic grievance politics with authoritarian, reactionist, ethnonationalist, and anti-modernist political agendas reflects a change in citizen's values that calls for novel explanations. PLEDGE offers such an explanation by focusing on dynamic interrelations between emotions, values, and identities. More precisely, it introduces two emotional mechanisms, EMRes and EMSoS whose influence on values differs significantly. While EMSoS allows individuals to maintain and reinforce their values, EMRes explains the change of values by showing how painful experiences emerging from actual or anticipated failure to live up to one's values leads individuals or groups to reject their values that are deemed undesirable or worthless, while new, more easily attainable values are adopted instead.

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3.8.2 Ideology (left/right)

Definition

Ideology, in the context of left-right orientation, refers to an organized set of beliefs and values that individuals hold regarding political, social, and economic issues, which typically align along a spectrum from left to right. The left is often associated with advocacy for social equality, government intervention in the economy, and progressive social policies, while the right tends to emphasize individualism, free-market principles, and traditional values. This orientation shapes individuals' political preferences, party affiliation, and policy attitudes.

How ideology contributes to PLEDGE conceptual framework

The left-right ideology serves as a foundational framework for understanding political beliefs and preferences within a spectrum. Traditionally, the left is associated with progressive values, advocating for social equality, governmental intervention in the economy, and the protection of civil rights, while the right emphasizes individualism, free-market principles, and preservation of traditional social structures. According to Bobbio (1994), this dichotomy reflects deeper philosophical underpinnings, where the left is aligned with ideals of social justice and equality, and the right is connected to the preservation of established norms and hierarchy. Inglehart and Norris (2003) highlight how this ideological divide has evolved, influenced by cultural and economic factors, leading to the emergence of new political movements and attitudes. Lipset (1996) emphasizes the significance of class structures and social cleavages in shaping these ideological orientations, illustrating how economic interests and cultural values intertwine to form distinct political identities. Together, these perspectives enrich the understanding of how left-right ideology functions as a critical lens for analyzing political behavior and societal change. PLEDGE hypothesizes left ideology to associate more closely with EMSoS and right ideology with EMRes, although there is some evidence on EMRes also in progressive left in contemporary identity politics (Brown, 1993, Campbell & Manning, 2018).

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3.8.3 Victimhood identity

Definition

Traditionally, the status of a person of being harmed or wronged, either by intentional human action (e.g. in mass atrocities, wars, or intergroup conflicts) or by natural catastrophes (Vollhardt, 2018; Alexander et al., 2004). More recently, claims of victimhood have become prevalent also among groups that have seen their privileged social status crumbling (Bebout, 2019; Chouliaraki, 2024).

How victimhood identity contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Politics of victimhood is the latest mode of identity politics or politics of recognition that highlights victimhood as the core of political identity. Victimhood is a claim on justice, and victim status authorizes an aggrieved party to demand recognition and reparation of wrongs or harms inflicted, and therefore it is a sought-after identity in politics.

Recent studies recognize victimhood as the core axis of EMRes (Salmela & Capelos, 2021; see also Abraham & Barreto, 2024; Sharafutdinova, 2020; Campbell & Manning, 2018; Hoggett, 2018; Horwitz, 2018). PLEDGE expects resentimentful victimhood to associate with lack of empathy (Gabay et al., 2020), moral elitism (Gabay et al., 2020; Salmela & Capelos, 2021; Demertzis, 2020), competitive or exclusive victimhood (Schori-Eyal et al., 2017; Young & Sullivan, 2016; Szabo, 2020), inability to forgive; rumination of victimhood and emotions associated with it (Demertzis, 2020; Salmela & Capelos, 2021; Hoggett, 2018), inability to overcome the victim position perpetuating powerlessness, self-pity, and moral hypernesia (Demertzis, 2020; Brown, 1993), dependence upon benefits that accrue to victim status (Jacoby, 2015; Brown, 1993), and collective narcissism (Capelos et al., 2024) Instead, PLEDGE expects to find correlation of victimhood identities mediated by EMSoS with empathy towards other victims Inclusive victimhood (Vollhardt, 2015); ability to forgive and avoid rumination through reconciliation with perpetrators and mourning the losses (Demertzis, 2019); and ability to overcome victimhood and become survivors by integrating themselves into democratic society through political recognition of victimhood and restorative justice (Jacoby, 2015). Victimhood identities are associated with intergroup hostility (Schori-Eyal et al., 2014), conspiracy theories (Bilewicz & Liu, 2020), disinformation and “fake news” (Roberts & Wahl-Jørgensen, 2020), diminished political efficacy (Armaly & Enders, 2021), and affective polarization (Gharib & Boler, 2021).

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3.8.4 Partisan identity

Definition

Partisan identity can be understood as a form of group identification, going beyond policy preferences, and involving emotional and social dimensions that can align closely with other forms of social identity (Huddy, 2001).

How partisan identity contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

PLEDGE does not have hypotheses about the relationship of partisan identity to the emotional mechanisms of resentment and solidarity-oriented sharing, or involvement in anti- or prodemocratic movements. However, we hypothesise that the partisan identity of groups operating EMSoS motivates constructive and purposive political action, whereas the partisan identity of groups operating on EMRes manifests as protests and dormant or active support for violent, destructive political action.

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3.8.5 Group identification

Definition

Group identification refers to how individuals perceive themselves as members of specific social groups, with this identification significantly influencing their attitudes, behaviors, and social dynamics. This identification can foster a sense of belonging, shape group norms, and impact intergroup relations.

How group identification relates to PLEDGE conceptual framework

Research on social identities (Tajfel & Turner, 1986) notes the psychological processes involved in group identification, emphasizing how shared values, goals, and emotional ties can enhance solidarity among group members. Social identity theory notes that individuals get a portion of their self-concept from their membership in social groups, leading to in-group favoritism and out-group discrimination (Tajfel, 1982). Studies in political behaviour show that party affiliation can heavily influence voting patterns and civic engagement (Huddy, 2001). Group identification is also closely related to collective action and mobilization. When individuals strongly identify with a group, they are more likely to participate in collective efforts to achieve shared goals. This is evident in social movements, where group identity can motivate individuals to advocate for social change (Van Zomeren, Postmes, & Spears, 2008). PLEDGE hypothesizes that group identification in groups operating on EMSoS is stronger than in groups operating on EMRes in motivating the members to participate in collective efforts to achieve shared goals.

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3.9 Socio-cultural Triggers and Facilitators of EMs

3.9.1 The Culture of Narcissism

Definition

Societal trend characterized by an excessive focus on individual self-interest and self-absorption, often at the expense of community and interpersonal relationships, and associated with an insecure and unstable sense of the self (Lasch, 1979).

How the culture of narcissism contributes to PLEDGE conceptual framework

In PLEDGE we are interested in how societies which display individualistic and self-centered values also display particular emotional responses that facilitate resentimentful grievance politics. We expect that in societies characterized by narcissistic tendencies, individuals will prioritize personal grievances and validation over collective concerns, which can lead to polarized emotional climates and diminished social solidarity. This focus on self-interest can hinder the development of solidarity and trust or the ability to articulate shared narratives, ultimately affecting how grievances are expressed and addressed within political contexts. We will identify the pervasiveness of the Culture of Narcissism in contemporary societies and examine whether it presents alongside the emotional mechanisms of resentment vs solidarity-oriented sharing.

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3.9.2 Gender

Definition

Gender can be defined as a socially constructed set of roles, behaviors, expressions, and identities that a society considers appropriate for men, women, and people outside of the

binary framework (LGBTQ+). Unlike biological sex, which is typically associated with physical attributes, gender encompasses the meanings and expectations that cultures attach to notions of masculinity, femininity, and non-binary expressions. This concept highlights the dynamic and relational nature of gender, shaped by cultural, political, and economic forces, and the power structures that uphold them (Butler, 1990; West & Zimmerman, 1987).

How gender contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

A gendered perspective on grievances highlights the discursive and narrative differentiation often made in Western theorizing between masculinity and femininity, where the latter is conceptualized as either the opposite of masculinity (the rational male vs. the emotional female), as its inferior (strong male needed to protect its weaker female counterpart), or as its straightforward equal (since man equals woman there is little need to look at gender) (Tavris, 1992, p. 27-30; Ahmed, 2005). Within this process of overgeneralizations, women's and minorities' identities have often been constructed around a lack of independence and autonomy, a lack of subjectivity in the modernist sense of the word. This lack of subjectivity has caused women's and minorities' subordination to appear natural, as primordial as consciousness itself (Beauvoir, 1952, in Tickner, 1996; Yuval-Davis, 1997), while it reflects intersecting racist, gendered, heteronormative and classicist patterns of social relations. Moreover, discourses on toxic masculinity have not only become more entrenched in the public sphere but have also come to characterize democratic politics in which voters are mobilized based on emotional appeals to a masculinist logic and a promise to protect the nation from exogenous threat (Norocel et al., 2020). Such a logic is also evident in the backlash against feminist ideas, with the latter being perceived as threats to the masculinist underpinnings of the nation.

PLEDGE expects EMRes to explain the emotions behind the rise of 'angry white men', which find a home in the discourses of antidemocratic grievance politics and in the idea that gender politics and feminism have gone too far. This reinforces the grip of this mechanism, which maintains a sense of loss and entitlement in the face of economic, social and cultural changes, feeding the notion that democracy and mainstream politics fail to represent the interests of those 'angry white men' (Capelos et al., 2022; Nicholas & Agius, 2018, p. 4).

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3.9.3 Conspiracy theories

Definition

“A conspiracy theory is the usually baseless assumption that a group of evildoers, the conspirators, are secretly manipulating events to achieve sinister goals” (Butter, 2020, p. 3)

How conspiracy theories contribute to PLEDGE conceptual framework

Although conspiratorial thinking has been always present in public life in all societies and in all historical periods, the current proliferation of conspiracy theories via social media, particularly the mainstreaming of formerly fringe ideas (Barkun, 2015) and a new conspiracism that sheds the attempt of explanation in favor of bare assertion (Rosenblum & Muirhead, 2019) can be seen as detrimental to democratic deliberations and has contributed to the perfect storm for the crisis of democracy and public knowledge. As reactionary rhetoric is replete of conspiratorial allegations (Shorten, 2015) and belief in specific conspiracy theories and advocacy of conspiracy mentality are integral elements not only of populism but of grievance politics too, PLEDGE will pay attention to both conspiracy theories endorsement and conspiracy mentality.

Conspiracy theories have been frequently yet inconsistently linked to political emotions and grievances. Wunderlich (in review) provides a comprehensive mapping of emotions evoked or addressed in conspiratorial discourses and theorizes that conspiracy theories can facilitate

and reciprocally be driven by emotional mechanisms. This is achieved because conspiracy theories, as cultural products that offer specific interpretations of political events, provide narrative templates through which individuals can reappraise their powerless and suppressed emotions like inefficacious anger or diffuse anxiety. Conspiracist discourses then enable the projection of such individual-level input emotions onto new objects (e.g. malicious conspirators, minorities or the mainstream), thus allowing for their transformation into more assertive, political and collectivized output emotions, that can be enacted and expressed.

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3.9.4 Victimhood narratives

Definition

Victimhood narratives are stories or discourses through which individuals or groups frame their experiences of suffering or oppression to assert identity, seek recognition, and mobilize for social change. These narratives can serve as a means for marginalized communities to claim their rights and articulate their grievances, and as a tool for dominant groups to maintain power by portraying themselves as victims of societal changes or challenges (Chouliaraki & Banet-Weiser, 2021; Jeffery & Candea, 2006; Barton Hronešová & Kreiss, 2024).

How victimhood narratives contribute to PLEDGE conceptual framework

Victimhood today operates as a ‘master’ signifier, a dominant communicative logic that is politically weaponized both by the marginalised and oppressed who claim power and recognition of their equal rights and the privileged who feel their existing power and hegemonic arrangements to be contested (Chouliaraki, 2024; Bebout, 2019). While arousing feelings of victimhood can be an effective motivator of political action, it is corrosive to democratic practices of dialogue and argumentation – in the extreme even to the adherence to the rule of law as aggrieved groups engage in a self-escalating cycle of conflict, payback, and competitive victimhood (Ditto & Rodriguez, 2021; Young & Sullivan, 2016). PLEDGE expects to find victimhood narratives especially in groups operating on EMRes, as victimhood is found to be the core axis of resentment (Salmela & Capelos, 2021).

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3.9.5 Feeling and Display Rules, Emotional Labor

Definition

“Feeling rules are what guide emotion work by establishing the sense of entitlement or obligation that governs emotional exchanges” (Hochschild, 1983, p. 56)

“Emotional display rules are underlying principles that guide us to make decisions either consciously or unconsciously to express or not to express our emotions (Ekman & Friesen, 1969; Hochschild, 1983; Isenbarger & Zembylas, 2006; Schutz et al., 2009; Chang, 2020, p. 2)

Emotional labor is the emotional energy spent to regulate regulation of emotions to meet social, political, cultural, or organizational expectations (Hochschild, 1983; Grandey, 2000)

Neighbouring concepts

Affective practices, emotion regulation

Funded by
the European Union

How feeling and display rules and emotional labor contribute to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

PLEDGE examines how feeling and display rules shape emotional mechanisms like EMRes and EMSoS, influencing social cohesion and political behavior. It hypothesizes that EMSoS thrives under rules promoting sincere emotional expression, while EMRes dominates in environments that discourage openness, such as those enforcing "stiff upper lip" norms. PLEDGE also aims to develop strategies to foster EMSoS.

Feeling rules regulate emotional norms within social and political contexts, affecting grievance politics and democratic engagement. Emotional mechanisms transform unconscious feelings like envy, shame, and inefficacious anger into conscious expressions, often managed through emotional labor—efforts to align emotions with social expectations (see Salmela and Capelos 2021). Emotional labor, as described by Hochschild (1983), involves surface or deep acting, shaping how individuals channel grievances into constructive solidarity or divisive resentment. Solidarity-oriented sharing, emphasizing empathy and unity, can counteract grievances, fostering resilience and mobilization (Grandey, 2000).

By analyzing these dynamics, PLEDGE provides insights into how emotions can both undermine and support democratic engagement, depending on the norms and labor shaping emotional expression.

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3.9.6 Affective practices

Definition

“An affective practice typically pulls together or orders in relation to each other patterns of body/brain activity, patterns of meaning-making, feelings, perceptions, cognition and memories, interactional potentialities and routines, forms of accountability, appraisals and evaluations, subject positions and histories of relationships.” (Wetherell, 2013, p. 236)

How affective practices contribute to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Affective practices refer to the ways emotions are expressed, shared, and cultivated within groups. In the PLEDGE framework, these practices help explain the emotional dynamics behind grievance politics in both pro- and anti-democratic movements. Affective practices aligned with EMSoS foster a collective environment that encourages the expression and transformation of negative emotions into pro-democratic resentment, promoting solidarity and collective political action. Practices such as solidarity, gratitude, and empathy help individuals connect emotionally, build a sense of belonging, and deepen group identity, enhancing pro-democratic engagement. In contrast, affective practices aligned with EMRes channel grievances into negative emotions like hatred, contempt, and bitter resentment, creating divisions and polarizing groups. This leads to a victim mentality and collective narcissism, deepening social fractures and diminishing cooperation. EMRes-driven practices hinder democratic cohesion by promoting polarization and hostility, making dialogue and compromise difficult. PLEDGE theorizes that such practices create a toxic emotional landscape that undermines democratic values and perpetuates conflict rather than fostering positive change.

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3.9.7 Emotional governance

Definition

In its broad sense, Emotional governance refers to the ways in which societies, political institutions, and cultural systems establish norms and expectations around emotional expression and regulation. It encompasses the "feeling rules" (Hochschild, 1979) that dictate which emotions are acceptable or unacceptable to express in specific contexts, and the emotional narratives promoted by political and social institutions that shape collective

identity and behavior. Emotional governance involves a complex interplay between emotions, power, and social control, using narratives, rituals, and practices to both align and discipline individual and collective emotional expressions (Solomon, 2012; Edkins, 2003). In its more restricted version, emotional governance is a top-down deliberate and sophisticated attention, through mass-mediated communications, to the emotional dynamics of the public exerted by political agents and corporations (Richards, 2007).

How emotional governance contributes to PLEDGE conceptual framework

The EM typology can be used to examine how political actors and institutions regulate emotions by providing individuals, groups, and states meanings and a sense of what is 'appropriate and inappropriate' in terms of behavior and feelings.

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3.10 Political Triggers and Facilitators of EMs

Emotional governance scholarship pays attention to emotional regimes setting society-wide norms for appropriate emotional expressions through feeling rules, official rituals, and discursive practices (Bell, 2006; Bevir & Rhodes, 2010; Bleiker & Hutchison, 2014; Connolly, 2005; Edkins, 2003; Holland & Solomon, 2014; Huysmans, 2006; Solomon, 2012; Weldes, 1999). Narrative and discourse analysis studies highlight how individuals, groups, and political leaders make sense of themselves and the world in emotional terms. In a narrative sense, this involves a focus on how stories (narratives) of the past and visions of the future are emotionally constructed and reconstructed considering present circumstances (Andrews, 2014; McAdams, 1985; Somers, 1994). In a discursive sense, it means going beyond language in linguistic terms to look at the overall meanings conveyed by language in context, where 'context' refers to the social, cultural, political and historical background of the discourse in which particular emotions emerge (Wodak, 2020). The EM typology can be used to examine how political actors and institutions regulate emotions by providing individuals, groups, and states meanings and a sense of what is 'appropriate and inappropriate' in terms of behavior and feelings.

3.10.1 *Styles of leadership*

Definition

In PLEDGE, the study of leadership styles focuses on understanding how different emotional approaches influence group dynamics and political mobilization. Leadership styles can range from authoritarian and charismatic to transformational, and these styles engage with emotions in distinct ways. PLEDGE will study how leaders employ these specific styles and their blended combinations to cultivate emotional connections, shape feeling and display rules within movements, and promote emotional mechanisms (EMRes or EMSoS) that align with their political agendas.

Authoritarian leadership is a leadership style which often employs emotional appeals that foster obedience, fear, and dependency (Altemeyer, 1981). Authoritarian leaders may evoke EMRes, reinforcing resentment, antagonism, and a rigid adherence to hierarchical norms. These leaders heighten insecurities and simultaneously position themselves as protectors against external threats, with the aim to promote group unity through shared grievances and directing hostility toward perceived out-groups (Duckitt, 2001).

Charismatic leadership is a leadership style which promotes emotional rapport and loyalty through compelling rhetoric and personal magnetism. Charismatic leaders inspire followers through intense emotional experiences, a sense of solidarity and shared purpose (Bass, 1985).

Transformational leadership is a leadership style characterized by its focus on collective goals, empathy, and emotional intelligence, and it is the leadership style which aligns with the principles of EMSoS. Transformational leaders engage in “inspirational motivation” and “individualized consideration,” fostering pro-social emotions that encourage group cohesion and mutual support (Burns, 1978; Bass & Riggio, 2006). Through positive emotional appeals, transformational leaders help create a sense of collective identity and purpose within democratic movements, like those seen in environmental and social justice initiatives.

How leadership styles contribute to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

PLEDGE studies leadership styles, in order to provide insights into how leaders foster emotional environments, influencing the norms and behaviors of their followers, and therefore, the broader emotional climate within political contexts. PLEDGE expects to find associations between toxic forms of leadership and EMRes. Leaders who engage in demagoguery may capitalize on populist resentment and nationalist pride, channeling followers’ grievances toward a common out-group and creating an “us versus them” mentality (Eatwell, 2006). This is particularly evident in anti-democratic movements where leaders use exclusionary tactics, fostering antagonism through emotional appeals that reinforce a sense of loss or victimhood (Norris & Inglehart, 2019).

Furthermore, the study of leadership styles within PLEDGE recognizes that authoritarian and charismatic leadership styles are not inherently opposed; rather, they frequently work in tandem to reinforce and amplify one another, especially within the framework of populist authoritarianism. These styles when combined enable populist authoritarian leaders to harness the stability of a rigid authority structure and the mobilizing power of emotional appeal, thus reinforcing their control over followers. Populist authoritarian leaders use charismatic traits to attract and rally supporters, presenting themselves as exceptional figures who embody the collective will of “the people” and standing in stark opposition to established elites or perceived enemies. Charismatic elements enable them to captivate followers, fostering a sense of loyalty and personal connection, while authoritarian traits maintain control and enforce compliance within the movement. Such leaders often portray themselves as protectors against external threats or moral decay, invoking a sense of shared grievance or crisis that necessitates their strong, decisive leadership (Salmela & Capelos, 2021).

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3.10.2 Policymaking

Definition

Policymaking is the process through which governmental and organizational entities identify, formulate, and implement policies to address societal issues and achieve specific goals. This process typically involves multiple stages, including agenda setting, policy formulation, decision-making, implementation, and evaluation. Policymaking is influenced by various factors, including political, economic, social, and emotional dimensions, requiring collaboration among diverse stakeholders (Fisher & Miller, 2007; Howlett & Ramesh, 2003; Howlett & Giest, 2012).

How policymaking contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

PLEDGE endeavors to create a more responsive and emotionally attuned policymaking environment capable of effectively navigating the challenges posed by grievance politics.

The challenge lies in identifying the steps that can (re)establish communication bridges and trust between citizens and political and policy actors, especially when distributive policy measures are insufficient or not immediately available. Policymakers must prioritize emotional sensitivity and sensibility to facilitate dialogue and build trust, recognizing that the emotional landscape of grievance politics can lead to polarization if not addressed properly.

Furthermore, there is an opportunity to harness the emotional sensitivity inherent in democratic innovations to co-create prototypes for a democratic infrastructure that encourages constructive and pro-democratic expressions of grievances. By fostering environments where citizens feel heard and validated, policymakers can effectively mitigate the adversarial nature of grievance politics.

Addressing the puzzle of the emotional economy of grievance politics can potentially repair compromised trust in democratic governance. As highlighted in the European Democracy

Action Plan, “Democracy cannot be taken for granted – it needs to be actively nurtured and defended.”

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3.10.3 Emotions in Policy Processes and Practices

Policy processes, traditionally understood as “a struggle for determination of meanings” consider conflicting values and beliefs (Yanow, 1996, p. 19, 230). Fischer (2010) has similarly argued emotions are inherent to deliberative processes, underscoring the need to study the central role of emotions in the policy process. However, we do not have much data on how effective the integration of emotions has been into policy processes and practices, or whether this integration is meeting citizens' emotional needs. What is needed is a critical examination of current policy practices focusing on achieving this aim, while identifying those preventing or limiting its realization. Crises like the Russo-Ukrainian war, the pandemic, and the climate-energy crisis, offer an opportunity to study whether policies launched at different levels of policy making (EU vs national) were designed with the aim to address pragmatic needs arising from the crises, as well as citizens' emotional needs.

Interpretative Practice Analysis (IPrA) reconstructs the ‘dispositional logic’ of practical knowledge and constructs the ‘positional logic’ through the interpretation of intersubjective rules of the game (Pouliot, 2008) and sheds light the practices of policymakers, diplomats, negotiators, and participants who engage with actors in the emotional economy of grievance politics (Adler-Nissen, 2008). Similarly, Interpretive Policy Analysis (IPA, Yanow 1996) pays attention to the affective side of politics, policy processes, and contestation (Griggs & Howarth, 2008), engaging with values, identities, and emotions in the policy process.

3.10.4 New Communication Technologies and Social Media

Definition

New communication technologies refer to the digital tools and platforms that facilitate the creation, sharing, and exchange of information through various media. This includes social media, mobile apps, extended reality/virtual reality, and artificial intelligence. These technologies enable instant communication and access to a vast array of content, fundamentally altering how individuals engage with each other and with political processes.

How new communication technologies and social media contribute to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

PLEDGE recognizes that as the boundaries between real and virtual worlds blur, the manipulation of communication technologies by various actors—including political entities, interest groups, and foreign adversaries—has a profound impact on how citizens perceive and engage with politics. These actors often exploit emotional triggers to sway public opinion, leading to an environment where emotional responses can overshadow rational discourse. Consequently, understanding the intricacies of this emotional landscape is crucial for fostering informed citizenry and is central to PLEDGE aims. Considering these developments, PLEDGE tackles a pressing question: how can we promote emotional intelligence and critical thinking as citizens navigate the complexities of digital spaces?

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3.10.5 Hybrid Media

Definition

Hybrid media refers to the merging of traditional media, such as newspapers, television, and radio, with digital and social media platforms, creating an interconnected media landscape where information circulates across multiple channels and formats (Chadwick, 2013; Bennett & Livingston, 2018).

How hybrid media contribute to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Hybrid media is an important realm where EMs play out and are facilitated. Citizen and policy actors communicate on these platforms spreading and circulating grievances, victimhood narratives, intergroup hostility, conspiracy theories, disinformation, and fake news, as well as blaming, scapegoating, and vilifying (Chadwick, 2013; Bennett & Livingston, 2018; Palau-Sampio, 2022). EMs allow us to predict, rather than simply describe these processes. We have found evidence of EMRes in social media platforms and digital content, like incel blogs, VR films and right-wing populist websites (Kazlauskaitė & Salmela, 2022; Kazlauskaitė, 2022; Capelos et al., 2024). These sites can also foster emancipatory politics and publics (Rambukkana, 2015) opening an opportunity to study EMSoS.

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3.10.6 Prosthetic memories

Definition

“A new form of memory”, which “emerges at the interface between a person and a historical narrative about the past, at an experiential site such as a movie theater or museum,” where “the person does not simply apprehend a historical narrative but takes on a more personal, deeply felt memory of a past through which he or she did not live” (Landsberg 2004, p. 2; Berger, 2007).

How prosthetic memories contribute to PLEDGE conceptual framework

Since VR experiences are assimilated into autobiographical memory (Kisker et al., 2021; Schöne et al., 2019, 2023), they shape users’ beliefs and understanding of who they are and can become, how they relate to others, how they evaluate the significance of past events, the futures they imagine, and how they plan for those futures (Conway, 2005; Fivush, 2011). Central to the conceptual framework of PLEDGE, VR is the medium of and for grievance politics. VR is commonly used to portray the experiences of oppressed, marginalized, traumatized people who have faced various adversities and discrimination (Gruenewald & Witteborn, 2022). Both VR and 360-degree non-fiction videos frequently engage themes of war and conflict, refugee experiences, disability, incarceration, impact of climate change, various forms of oppression and discrimination. Difficult social topics are introduced experientially, promising the audience an encounter with the lived realities of hardship. By facilitating prosthetic memories of emotionally charged immersive experiences, VR can

contribute to EMRes and EMSoS (Kazlauskaitė, 2022, 2023, 2024). The influence of VR on emotions, values, identities, and beliefs can lead to support for and active involvement in anti-democratic or pro-democratic forms of grievance politics.

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3.11 Political Preferences and Behaviors

3.11.1 Political Participation

Definition

Political participation is defined as those actions of private citizens by which they seek to influence or support government and politics (Milbrath & Goel, 1977, p. 2).

How political participation contributes to PLEDGE conceptual framework

In the PLEDGE conceptual framework, political participation is seen as a multifaceted, purposeful activity where citizens engage with the political system in both conventional and unconventional ways, ranging from voting to activism (Milbrath & Goel, 1977; Kaase & Marsh, 1979).

PLEDGE understands that political participation is not limited to voting or campaigning. Rather, it encompasses a wide spectrum of activities from passive engagement, such as paying taxes, to active roles, such as joining protests or contacting public officials. This variety captures the breadth of involvement in politics and reflects motivations, identities, values, as well as emotionality. Equally, grievance politics is carried out through multiple forms of political action ranging from apathy to heated contentious political behavior. With the above in mind, the PLEDGE conceptual framework allows for an in-depth analysis of how input and output emotions of EMRes and EMSoS are linked to political actions, whether collective or individualized. PLEDGE theorises on the affective maps of political engagement to understand the emotional currents that drive different forms of participation within grievance politics.

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3.11.2 Escalating political dissent

Political radicalization, rejection of democratic norms, acts of civil disobedience, and outgroup hatred are constructs that highlight the emotional and behavioural dimensions of escalating political dissent. These concepts are interconnected, capturing various aspects and expressions of political disaffection and ideological extremism. Each contributes to understanding the pathways through which grievances transform into more radical, and often destabilizing anti-democratic political action.

Definition

Political radicalization refers to the process by which individuals and groups shift toward adopting extreme beliefs or advocating actions and systemic changes that challenge or destabilize the political and social order (McCauley & Moskaleiko, 2008)

The **rejection of democratic norms** is one of the key outcomes of the process of gradual disillusionment with democratic institutions, often seen as corrupt, elitist, or ineffectual (Dalton, 2004).

Acts of civil disobedience are expressions of resistance to authority and efforts to disrupt or challenge the status quo. They may involve nonviolent resistance as well as confrontational and violent acts (Sharp, 1973).

Outgroup hatred refers to the intense negative feelings and beliefs about members of an outgroup perceived as different or opposing. It involves hostility, moral disdain, and a devaluation of the outgroup's worth, often based on identity markers such as race, religion, nationality, or political ideology. Outgroup hatred heightens polarization and promotes exclusionary and often aggressive behaviours (Allport, 1954; Tajfel & Turner, 1979)

How escalating political dissent contributes to PLEDGE conceptual framework

Escalating political dissent in the form of radicalization, rejection of democratic norms, acts of civil disobedience, and outgroup hatred are deeply intertwined with the emotional dynamics of grievance politics. The emotional mechanism of resentment, manifest as deep-seated resentment and frustration born from perceived social and political injustice, can fuel behaviours and attitudes that challenge or undermine existing social and political structures, typically as an urgent and violent reaction to perceived systemic inequalities or marginalization.

Radicalization, the process of gradual shift towards extreme views and willingness to pursue significant changes (McCauley & Moskaleiko, 2008), is more than often emotionally charged, with resentment giving impetus to non-institutionalized or even violent actions. Extant research suggests that individuals radicalize when their grievances are perceived as unmet by

democratic or peaceful means (Borum, 2011), leading to a sense of moral outrage and anger directed at perceived oppressors or “the system” (Doosje et al., 2016). In resentment, a deep sense of powerlessness fosters a desire to reclaim agency or justice through dramatic, sometimes radical actions.

The **rejection of democratic norms** is often portrayed as justified in narratives that describe democracy as ineffective, corrupt, or incapable of addressing fundamental societal issues. When citizens feel persistently and repeatedly unheard or marginalized, they may view democratic processes as tools that serve only elite interests, reinforcing a sense of alienation (Dalton, 2004). These conditions are ripe for resentment, which can through processes of transvaluation be expressed as the desire to follow those who seek to dismantle democratic structures in favour of alternatives that align with the newly perceived need for justice and empowerment. Authoritarian leaders and forms of governance that promise swift, decisive action, can be appealing to those frustrated by the perceived inefficacy of democratic processes, and who have transmuted their feelings of being repressed to feeling morally righteous victims.

Acts of civil disobedience, traditionally understood as nonviolent, principled resistance to laws or policies deemed unjust, can in the context of grievance politics become a moral statement and a way to express resentment. When citizens feel aggrieved and have a chance to actively challenge the authority of those perceived to be perpetuating their grievances, acts of civil disobedience can be imbued by righteousness and moral urgency, and as a necessary means to expose what is perceived as systemic injustice, even via extreme measures.

Outgroup hatred is linked to the resentimentful emotional underpinnings of grievance politics, as outgroups are perceived as threats or obstacles, and are cast as morally inferior or corrupt. Outgroups in this context become scapegoats for societal and political grievances, where frustration is directed away from the self and the ingroup, towards the perceived ‘enemy’ other. While hatred towards outgroups can in the context of resentment galvanize ingroup bonds, these bonds are expected to be shallow and qualitatively different from the solidarity bonds that exist in non-resentimentful group dynamics. Venting resentment through outgroup hatred perpetuates cycles of animosity and blame, cementing ‘us vs. them’, without addressing the threats and obstacles that give rise to resentment.

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3.11.3 Political alienation, apathy, powerlessness

Definitions

Political alienation refers to a condition where individuals feel disconnected and estranged towards political systems, institutions, and political processes. It is a multi-dimensional phenomenon characterized by a sense of powerlessness, normlessness, frustration, and disillusionment, leading individuals to perceive political participation and engagement as futile or irrelevant (Lane, 1965).

Political apathy refers to the state of indifference towards political processes and issues, and it is marked by lack of engagement (Lazarsfeld, Berelson, & Gaudet, 1944).

Powerlessness is defined as a feeling of lacking control or influence over important political or societal outcomes, often accompanied by a perception that one's actions are inconsequential in effecting change (Seeman, 1959).

How political alienation, political apathy, and powerlessness contribute to PLEDGE conceptual framework

In the context of grievance politics, **political alienation** can promote political dissatisfaction and non-democratic forms of mobilization. When individuals feel alienated, they may experience humiliation, frustration, and shame which through resentment can be transmuted to hostility toward the system and its representatives. In resentment, feelings of exclusion and betrayal can shift from passive disillusionment to active resentment. This cycle of resentment and alienation can give rise to oppositional, anti-system sentiments, and make radical alternatives that promise greater change than mainstream politics appealing.

Political Apathy is crucial for understanding grievance politics because it reflects a broader emotional landscape that influences how individuals perceive and react to political injustices. When individuals experience repeated frustrations combined with the disillusionment that their voices are not heard or their concerns are dismissed, a cycle of apathy is likely to occur, sparked by powerless anger. This climate is fertile ground for resentment, while powerlessness further deters the individual from engaging effectively and critically in political processes that could address the original grievances. Apathy can exacerbate feelings of alienation and resentment toward political institutions, creating fertile ground for radicalization or extremist movements. When individuals feel politically apathetic, they may be more likely to seek alternative forms of political expression that can be more radical, as conventional channels seem ineffective. This is particularly relevant in societies facing significant crises or inequalities, where grievances can mount and generate widespread discontent.

Powerlessness relates closely to the emotional mechanism of resentment. When individuals believe they are repeatedly and unjustly deprived of power or agency by larger systems, they harbor powerless anger towards those in authority or societal elites. The resentment stemming from powerlessness is not an action prone resentment. It deepens grievances, by amplifying the emotional weight of perceived injustices and contributing to a cycle where powerlessness, through resentment, intensifies the grievances and promotes disengagement (Salmela & Capelos, 2021).

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3.12 New Approaches to Democratic Society

3.12.1 Democratic Innovations

Definition

Democratic innovations refer to new practices, processes, or structures that enhance democratic governance and participation. These innovations often leverage technology to foster citizen engagement, improve transparency, and create more inclusive decision-making processes. Examples include participatory budgeting, deliberative democracy forums, and online platforms that facilitate civic engagement and policy input (Bächtiger et al., 2018)

How democratic innovations contribute to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

In PLEDGE, democratic innovations contribute to emotionally sensitive governance and policy-making. Democratic innovations are intended to incorporate a deeper understanding of citizens' emotional needs and grievances. By doing so, these innovations help prevent the escalation of anti-democratic grievances and foster constructive political behavior. Democratic innovations are closely tied to the design of deliberative practices that actively engage citizens in dialogue and decision-making processes.

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3.12.2 Democratic Design

Definition

Democratic Design is an approach to think about democracy, how to improve it and to design democratic innovations to that end (Saward, 2021).

How democratic design contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

PLEDGE adopts the democratic design approach to identify and produce emotion-sensitive democratic designs (see also next entry). The Democratic Design framework as formulated by Saward (i) is problem-driven: it identifies and creates democratic innovations and interventions in response to democratic problems or democratic incompleteness; (ii) is systemic in its approach (in contrast to ‘single institution (re)design’); (iii) rejects the limiting, forced choice between existing models of democracy (participatory, deliberative, (post)representative etc.) in favor of a ‘mix and match’ approach where practices and devices based in various models can be sequenced and layered; (iv) stimulates ambition and creativity: democratic designers imagine what democracy can be and the ways in which it can be enacted, ‘thinking the as-yet-unthought’ (Saward, 2021, p. 47); (v) is not merely academic, but constitutes ‘theory for practice’: democratic principles are ‘thought together’ with practices that enact those principles; (vi) is context specific: democratic designers design for a specific time and place. The feminist take on democratic design prescribes that regardless of other democratic shortcomings democratic designers address, they start from the inequality they are confronted with and are committed to make equality happen (Celis and Childs 2024).

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3.12.3 Emotion-sensitive democratic design

Definition

Emotion-sensitive democratic designs are democratic innovations that are purposively designed to strengthen pro-democratic emotions and emotional mechanisms (Legein and Celis forthcoming D6.1).

How emotion-sensitive democratic design contributes to the PLEDGE conceptual framework

Emotion-sensitive democratic designs depart from the idea that emotions are problematic and need to be banned from both the processes and outcomes of policy- and decision-making. In contrast, emotion-sensitive democratic designs (i) fully acknowledge that emotions are intrinsic to all political actors and drive political behaviors, including their willingness to participate (and keep participating) in democratic policy-making and decision-making processes; and (ii) implement practices and processes to initiate, maintain or foster pro-democratic emotions and emotional mechanisms, and/or to limit, stop or reverse anti-democratic ones.

PLEDGE aims to identify and co-design with stakeholders emotion-sensitive democratic innovations that (i) foster pro-democratic emotions and reduce the anti-democratic ones (with pro- and anti-democratic emotions as identified by the PLEDGE team); (ii) initiate, maintain or further the emotional mechanism of solidarity-oriented sharing and/or limit, stop, or reverse the emotional mechanism of resentment.

References

Legein, T. and Celis, K. D6.1 (forthcoming)

4. Citation

4.1 Citing the PLEDGE Conceptual Framework

As the PLEDGE Conceptual Framework is a *living document* subject to updates, it is essential to include version details when referencing it in your reports. This ensures transparency, reproducibility, and clarity in your methodology. Please follow these guidelines:

- ✓ **Standardized Reference Name:**
Cite the document as:
“*Research Report: PLEDGE Conceptual Framework v.1*” (or the applicable version number).
- ✓ **Include the DOI:**
Always add the assigned DOI to ensure persistent access and traceability.

